

IRRI 1997-1998

Biodiversity
Maintaining
the Balance

IRRI's MISSION STATEMENT

Our Goal

To improve the well-being of present and future generations of rice farmers and consumers, particularly those with low incomes

Our Objectives

To generate and disseminate rice-related knowledge and technology of short- and long-term environmental, social, and economic benefit and to help enhance national rice research systems

Our Strategy

We pursue our goal and objectives through

- Interdisciplinary ecosystem-based programs in major rice environments
- Scientific strength from discipline-based divisions
- Anticipatory research initiatives exploring new scientific opportunities
- Conservation and responsible use of natural resources
- Sharing of germplasm, technologies, and knowledge
- Participation of women in research and development
- Partnership with farming communities, research institutions, and other organizations that share our goal

Our Values

Our actions are guided by a commitment to

- Excellence
- Scientific integrity and accountability
- Innovation and creativity
- Diversity of opinion and approach
- Teamwork and partnership
- Service to clients
- Cultural diversity
- Gender consciousness
- Indigenous knowledge
- Environmental protection

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Biodiversity Maintaining the Balance

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SHARING THE RESPONSIBILITY

From the time the first wild rice grains were gathered thousands of years ago, the genus *Oryza* has fed more people longer than any other. Grown by farmers for at least 6,000 years, rice has richly influenced the cultures and lives of billions of people, nourishing their bodies and spirits from birth until death.

Today, rice is the staple food for nearly 3 billion people. By 2025, that number will be a stag-

gering 4.6 billion. Nearly twice as much rice will have to be harvested to feed these people. Saving what remains of the Earth's most valuable resource—biological diversity—is essential for coping with this demand to supply more food.

The natural diversity of traditional rice varieties, nurtured by farmers for generations, and the wild relatives of rice contain the genes for creating better rice plants that can produce more grain. The diversity of the many species living in the rice landscape must also be looked

to for managing rice pests and adaptation to other environmental stresses.

Fifteen years ago, the term "biodiversity" had not even been coined. Today, it is a household word and a focus of concern for the general public. From the landscape to the species to the gene, biodiversity is the foundation of our planet's health and humanity's future food supply.

Agriculture, although sometimes seen as a foe of biodiversity, has its very roots in biological diversity and could not exist without it. In fact,

agricultural landscapes teem with life, and are complex, fascinating systems.

Scientists have convincingly shown that most invertebrate biodiversity exists in human-managed ecosystems, such as crop fields and forests. Tropical rice ecosystems provide a stunning example. IRRI scientists have counted more than 600 different insects, spiders, snails, mites, nematodes, small crustaceans, and vertebrate animals—such as frogs, rats, birds, and fish—in typical irrigated Philippine rice fields, and more than 760 in Indonesian rice fields.

When considering biodiversity research issues, we must look at the entire rice landscape—and not only the rice field—because pests and their natural enemy species do not limit their feeding and breeding activities to single fields. It is impossible to isolate the crop from its environment and the farmers who grow it—and who need to attain a decent living from the land without destroying it and the rich diversity it supports.

The permanency of the food base on which we depend, today and for generations to come, depends on caring for and wisely using the genetic diversity of rice and the natural resources of its landscape. Simply stated, we must maintain the balance.

Cooperation in conserving, using, and sharing rice genetic resources and developing ways to make use of biodiversity for sustainable pest management can make enormous contributions to the well-being of humanity. IRRI is committed to taking the lead in ensuring that rice genetic resources continue to benefit all rice-producing and -consuming peoples.

ROBERT HAVENER
Director General (Interim)

C. Dedolph, Madagascar

"Biodiversity, the planet's most valuable resource, is on loan to us from our children."

Biodiversity II: Understanding and Protecting Our Biological Resources

Using the Earth's biodiversity judiciously is vital for maintaining food security and reducing poverty. Global cooperation—from farmers to governments—is critical for maintaining the balance across the rice landscape.

Using Biodiversity

to Manage Pests

As long as people have been growing rice, insect pests, diseases, weeds, and rats have been lurking in the fields. Fortunately for farmers, so have spiders, parasitic wasps, and helpful fungi and bacteria that keep these pests under control.

But then came chemical pesticides. Their widespread use—and often misuse—has upset nature’s balance, polluted the environment, and sometimes even made farmers sick.

“A radical change is needed in the way people think about integrated pest management in tropical irrigated rice,” says Dr. K.L. Heong, IRRI entomologist. “IPM should be based on the contention that pesticides are *not* needed, rather than they are, meaning they would be used more judiciously.”

Farmers’ experiences provide evidence that rice can be grown successfully with less chemical pesticides. Through the project “Exploiting Biodiversity for Sustainable Pest Management,” IRRI scientists and their partners from around Asia are working to find ways to manage pests naturally in

“It’s not the sheer number of species in an ecosystem that’s truly critical; rather, it’s the roles they play.”

MICHAEL WAY
Emeritus Professor of Entomology
Imperial College of Science, Technology, and
Medicine, United Kingdom

Sampling stations (1-52) set up along a transect are being used to solve some of the mysteries of pest-natural enemy movement

intensive rice systems. The 3-year project, funded by the Asian Development Bank, aims to create economical, safe, and sustainable strategies that reduce farmers’ dependency on pesticides.

The Bountiful Rice Landscape

The rice landscape—the patchwork of fields and surrounding areas—is surprisingly rich in biodiversity. Home to more than simply the rice crop, it parallels some of the most diverse “natural” systems on earth. The irrigated rice ecosystem in the Philippines, for instance, contains nearly 700 different plants and animals—such as insects, spiders, snails, small crustaceans, frogs, and rats—most of which are not pests.

More than just the number of species in a habitat, biodiversity is the “variety of life forms, the ecological roles they perform, and the genetic diversity they contain;” it is fundamental to agriculture—and natural pest management.

“Biodiversity is about balancing the positives and negatives in a system,” says Dr. Heong. “It’s about the roles species play, how they interact, and how stable they are.”

It’s the Mix That Counts

Integrated pest management emphasizes using the best mix of biological control, host-plant resistance, and cultural practices to maintain low pest populations—plus pesticides, but only as a last resort. For pest management practices to be sustainable, they need to make use of what’s already in the farming community—and what makes sense to farmers.

Natural enemies of insect pests and antagonists of some plant diseases and weeds provide the basis for keeping pest populations below damaging levels. These natural biological controls—combined with specific field management practices and diverse rice varieties—provide a solid alternative to chemical pesticides, particularly for insect pests.

“Our goal is to pinpoint a few stable components of diversity within and around rice fields and manipulate them to develop sustainable, low-cost, and environmentally compatible ways to protect the crop,” explains Dr. Heong.

E.O. Wilson, an early advocate of biodiversity, called insects “the

*B.A. Wilcox. 1984. In McNeeley, J.A. and K.R. Miller, eds. *National Parks, Conservation and Development: The Role of Protected Areas in Sustaining Society*. Smithsonian Press.

M. Amongo

little things that run the world." In a rice field, insects are usually some of the most damaging pests, along with rats and snails. But a whole army of generalist and specialist predators and parasites is there to control the pests. A good example is the yellow stem borer: a hundred or so predator and parasite species prey on it at different stages of its life cycle.

When it comes to diseases, management practices are mainly based on resistance genes built into varieties combined with cultural controls; chemical fungicides are heavily used in only a few countries. Mixing varieties within fields and across fields provides other options. Microorganisms with the potential to suppress a range of plant diseases are plentiful on rice plants and in the soil—and could be used to manage these diseases.

Natural vegetation—weeds to most people—presents another challenge. "All nonrice plants in a field are not necessarily bad," says Martin Mortimer, IRRI weed ecologist. "If we can identify which weeds are good for natural enemies and bad for pests, we may recom-

mend that farmers selectively weed their fields. But managing the vegetation around the field edges will probably have even greater benefit for beneficial insects."

Changing the way farmers see nonrice vegetation will be a major challenge. "When farmers see grass, we want them to think 'that's good grass. That's where crickets live,'" Dr. Heong says.

Lighthouses in the Fields

As a major component of the ADB project, five "lighthouse" sites were established in 1997, one each in the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam and two in China, to illuminate how biodiversity can be tapped for sustainable pest management. Together these sites represent Asia's intensive rice ecosystems.

Transects, or narrow belts of vegetation traversing the rice landscape, were established at three sites. Regularly spaced sampling stations were set up along each transect. Scientists are developing and testing tools to sample insects, spiders, plant pathogens, and weeds to quantify their diversity

and associations, and to study changes in their intensity and influence on rice yields across a season.

"Our ultimate goal is to develop pest management strategies that increase rice yields and farm incomes year after year," says Paul Teng, IRRI plant pathologist.

Major emphasis is being placed on training rice pest management research teams at each site. Members are learning how to use modern biodiversity concepts and tools for developing sustainable pest management strategies.

During 1997, specific techniques and tools to sample arthropods, plant pathogens, and weed species were applied and used with good results. "We noticed that the diversity and intensity of insects, spiders, and weeds changed within a single season, but we don't know exactly why," explains Ken Schoenly, IRRI insect ecologist.

In 1997, regular sampling along the transects at three lighthouse sites was begun, and information on farmers' practices was collected. National scientists are enthusiastic about the work. "We need to under-

stand the mechanisms that will sustain low pest populations with minimal pesticide use," says La Pham Lan, one of the team members at the Vietnam site.

Cutting Across the Landscape

Characterizing an agroecosystem with such staggering biodiversity and such rich food webs presents scientists with a complicated challenge. As a prelude to the ADB project, four transects were pilot-tested at IRRI to determine their application to biological control.

Sampling stations were regularly spaced along the transects, dotting rice fields and bunds (the earthen dikes surrounding rice fields), other crop fields, abandoned fields, and roads.

"We're really interested in finding out where organisms are drawing their own lines in the sand and whether these lines change in magnitude or location with time," says Dr. Schoenly. "We're removing human perceptions and letting the creatures do the talking."

This work has already revealed that predators, pests, and parasitic

"We're trying to determine how insect pests and natural enemies perceive boundaries between rice and other plants to find natural ways to manage pests. Do these creatures actually view things the same way we do?"

KEN SCHOENLY
IRRI Insect Ecologist

wasps form distinctive groups along recognizable boundaries, such as the field edge, but have weaker boundaries within the field itself.

Looking Beyond the Rice Field

Scientists are eyeing the areas around the rice fields and the bunds to determine their roles in maintaining pests and predators.

For natural enemies to work for farmers, these creatures need year-round continuity of prey and places to live when there's no crop in the field. They often look to vegetation outside the field or head for the cracks in the soil. The plant-covered bunds around the fields may be particularly important.

In the past, plants in nonrice habitats have been accused of harboring insect pests, diseases, snails, and rats. The weed *Ipomoea aquatica*, for example, is home to snails during the off-season. Selectively removing it from fields may leave the mollusks high and dry.

"These nonrice habitats are undoubtedly home to some pests, but what about the insect preda-

tors?" asks Dr. Heong. "We're talking about creating the best possible mix where the positives outweigh the negatives."

Field shape may also matter: long, narrow rectangles of vegetation are likely to harbor more biodiversity than square fields of equal size, which is the reason transects were chosen as a tool to characterize that biodiversity.

Life in the Cracks

Large, diverse populations of natural enemies inhabit the dry, cracked soils during fallow periods in both irrigated and rainfed lowland rice fields. A veritable smorgasbord of creatures live in the crevices: mites, earthworms, crickets, spiders, ants, beetles, leafhoppers, and parasitic wasps.

Like other nonrice habitats and bunds, crevices may provide alternative sites for natural enemies of rice pests. Such cracks harbor these species across long, dry fallow periods by providing food and shelter, and hiding them from predators.

"Once the crop is planted, these fallow-season natural enemies can head off early season pest outbreaks because they're already where the action is taking place," Dr. Schoenly says. And this means farmers do not need to resort to pesticides.

Thinking Ahead

Improving rice yields, eradicating poverty, and protecting the environment will depend heavily on changing how farmers handle pests. The benefits of using biodiversity to manage pests in intensive rice systems must not be overlooked.

"We need to learn to accept living with pests at tolerable levels," says Dr. Heong. "No matter how hard we try, we'll never get rid of them all." ■

Scientists working together at the lighthouse site in Vietnam

Farmers Let Nature Do the Work

One farm family in the Philippines hasn't used a drop or granule of insecticide for the past 15 years—proof that under some conditions “farmers don't need to use insecticides in rice.”

“**I**n the early days, I was sometimes afraid,” says Lourdes Masajo. “I would go into the field and see some of the plants eaten by insects. I would ask my husband, who had a government job then, to visit the field to see if we should spray insecticides. He would say, ‘Forget it!’”

She and her husband Nanding are dedicated to insecticide-free rice farming. They haven't used any chemical insecticides for the past 15 years on their 24-hectare rice farm in Laguna Province. Their yields average 4.1 tons per hectare in the wet season and 6.6 tons per hectare in the dry season—notably higher than the provincial averages of 3.7 and 4.1 tons per hectare, respectively.

According to Mr. Masajo, using insecticides “breaks the natural balance.” If insecticides aren't applied, parasites and predators can manage the pest populations.

“The main problem farmers are facing is to resist applying insecticides in the face of ‘propaganda’ encouraging their use,” Mr. Masajo says adamantly. Through passive persuasion, most of the Masajos' 550 rice-farming neighbors in and around the village of Victoria have gradually stopped using insecticides on rice. For them, seeing is believing.

Before becoming a full-time farmer, Mr. Masajo worked on a large commercial rice farm where he observed that multiple insecticide applications intensified insect pest

problems. But in neighboring farmers' fields—people who were too poor to buy insecticides—spiders and other predators controlled the pests. His hypothesis was born: insecticides are not needed for rice farming.

“Twenty-nine seasons in 15 years have supported my hypothesis,” says the farmer confidently.

The Masajos have proven to themselves—and their neighbors—that insecticides are not needed to achieve high yields in rice. “We have no reservations that farmers around Asia can grow rice without chemical insecticides.” ■

The farmer and one of his hardworking friends

Friends Fighting Foes

Snapshots from the Landscape and Laboratory

Rice fields and the areas around them contain incredible biodiversity, whether crop or weed, predator or pest. When left alone to do their thing, this compendium of creatures, plants, and microbes will strike a harmonious balance that enables the rice crop to thrive—naturally.

Spiders: A Will to Kill

When it comes to controlling insect pests in rice, spiders make short order of the job. Naturally voracious, one spider can immobilize five brown planthopper nymphs or adults in two or three minutes.

Among the more than 300 diverse spiders living in and around irrigated rice fields in South and Southeast Asia, the wolf, jumping, and lynx spiders are legendary. “These spiders are the little murderers of rice pests,” says Bert Barrion, IRRI spider expert.

Spiders are incredibly finicky, too. If after biting its prey, a spider doesn’t get the right “juice,” it will reject the insect and hunt again.

Other predators, such as dragonflies or ants, eat the entire insect and then rest.

Habitats surrounding the fields provide important refuges in the off-season. “When the rice is harvested, it’s like having their homes demolished,” the expert explains. “The areas around a field serve as ‘guesthouses’ for spiders until the next rice crop.”

Maintaining healthy spider populations requires farmers to avoid doing certain things, the most important of which is not to apply pesticides.

Weed-Hungry Fungi

Weeds are an integral part of all rice ecosystems. Fortunately, so are fungal pathogens that attack weeds. Often defined as “any plant growing where it shouldn’t,” weeds in Asia annually choke out at least 100 million tons of rice from ever being produced. Fungal pathogens are being investigated as a novel way to economically

control some weeds in rice fields. It is anticipated that this biological control will become a component of an integrated weed management system that can reduce the heavy reliance on a single-factor approach—such as herbicide application.

Scientists have made the pathogens’ spores into suspensions and field-tested them as bioherbicides. The results have been relatively encouraging, but it will be some time before bioherbicides are on the market.

“Efficacy and durability, combined with practicality and economics, will govern the adoption of bioherbicides for controlling rice weeds,” explains IRRI weed scientist Alan Watson. If the scientists’ efforts succeed, resource-poor rice farmers in Asia, their environments, and their aching backs will be the winners.

A Home Away from Home for Wasps

Sometimes the plants growing next to the rice field are extremely important for the health of the rice crop.

Consider the tall, maize-like *Zizania caduciflora*, a popular vegetable of people living in China’s Yangtze Delta. Commonly grown along rice fields, *zizania* harbors the

planthopper *Saccharosydne procerus*—which does not attack rice. This insect serves as an alternative host for the egg parasitoid *Anagrus nilaparvatae*, one of the most important natural enemies of planthoppers that do feed on rice.

Tiny but mighty, egg parasitoids are nearly invisible wasps that lay their eggs on planthopper eggs. (The five brown eggs in the photograph are parasitized, the clear one is not.) The young wasps feed on the unhatched hoppers. When insecticides are not used in rice, natural enemies can nearly always control planthoppers.

“*Zizania* is the launching pad for the egg parasitoids to move into newly planted rice fields,” explains Xiaoping Yu, an entomologist from the Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences in Hangzhou, China, who is working with IRRI.

The next step: determining the roles other round-the-rice-field plants play in controlling pests and encouraging farmers to grow these plants.

B. Barrion

Where Did They Go? Crickets on the Move

Predatory crickets (*Metioche* and *Anaxipha* species), which feed on the eggs of stem borers and rice leaffolders, are insects on the move. But which habitats do they prefer? When? Why? And what are the implications for managing pests and the areas surrounding rice fields?

To trace the movements of crickets between rice and nonrice habitats, scientists are marking the insects with the chemical rubidium chloride. "Ultimately, we want to be able to recommend to farmers the kinds of

habitats that help the crickets, as well as the things they shouldn't do—such as burn vegetation," says Dr. Yu.

Tapping into Microbial Diversity on Seeds

Microorganisms naturally make themselves at home on rice seeds. Most don't seem to do much of anything. Some cause diseases, and a few actually come to the rescue of the helpless seeds and fight disease-causing fungi and bacteria. Scientists are focusing their attention on this last group—especially on the ones that seem to promote seed germination and enhance seedling vigor.

When seeds that exhibited particularly good vigor were washed and then other seeds were soaked in that water, those other seeds also showed excellent seedling vitality and growth compared with seeds soaked in plain water. These good microorganisms seem to be associated with both the fields and the varieties.

"We need to improve our understanding of these biological control agents so we can put them to work for farmers as an alternative to fungicides," says Tom Mew, IRRI plant pathologist.

Outpacing Bacterial Blight

Staying one step ahead of the wily bacterial blight pathogen has kept scientists on their toes for years.

Thanks to the widespread use of rice varieties with built-in resistance, epidemics are rare today. But new forms of the bacterial blight pathogen, *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*, are constantly evolving.

Researchers are using biotechnology tools—combined with the extraordinary diversity of rice—to outpace this disease. "Biotechnology allows us to look at the hidden diversity of resistance genes we otherwise couldn't see," says IRRI plant pathologist Hei Leung.

So far, more than 20 resistance genes have been identified. Scientists are pyramiding different combinations of them in ways that provide resistance to the broadest possible range of pathogen strains. Varieties with complex and durable bacterial blight resistance are the result. The wild

relatives of rice have also been excellent sources of resistance genes, particularly *Oryza longistaminata* and *O. minuta*.

Through the Asian Rice Biotechnology Network, scientists from the region are using these genes in ways that maximize their impact and durability in the local environments of each country.

Blast Proves a Devious Disease

Blast disease can devastate rice. A master of mutation, the devious fungal pathogen *Magnaporthe grisea* has proven extremely adaptable to many environments.

"Where modern rice varieties have been released in areas of India, the Philippines, and Vietnam, populations are relatively simple," explains IRRI plant pathologist Robert Zeigler. But where diverse traditional rice varieties predominate, such as in Northeast Thailand and the Himalayan region of India, the pathogen populations are many times more complex. Sexual—besides the usual asexual—reproduction cycles may affect the populations.

Because of these distinct differences in populations, scientists have learned that resistance gene combinations that combat blast in one area may be totally ineffective in another. "Understanding and characterizing the genetic makeup of blast populations is critical to developing and distributing rice varieties with effective resistance," explains Dr. Zeigler.

Ants: This Bund's for You

The bunds, or earthen dikes, around tropical irrigated rice fields support an abundant and sometimes extremely diverse ant community. Sixty-two species have been found in Philippine fields, with each occupying different niches and having its own strategies for survival.

"But the role they play in controlling rice insect pests—and how they interact with other predators—is not clear," says Michael Way, emeritus professor of entomology at the Imperial College of Science, Technology, and Medicine in the United Kingdom.

Solenopsis geminata, known as fire ants because of their vicious stings, flourish in disturbed, barren environments—such as the bunds of irrigated rice fields. But they disappear when the bunds are left undisturbed and become well vegetated. *Pheidole* species dominate then.

When farmers allow their fields to drain before reflooding, staggering numbers of ants march over the bare mud to feast on things such as golden apple snail eggs, planthopper eggs, and caterpillars—all enemies of the rice plants. ■

R. Cabrei

The wealth of rice genetic diversity is stunning. Conserving and sharing this priceless resource is a responsibility IRRI takes seriously.

Sharing the Seeds

For centuries, farmers have created and nurtured thousands of rice varieties—and saved and exchanged seeds. They saw diverse genetics as insurance for food security.

Today, rice feeds nearly 3 billion people, or almost half the world's population; by 2025, that number will be 4.6 billion. Developing improved rice varieties to feed them depends on the availability of the traditional varieties—and the wild relatives of rice—to serve as parents.

Both these genetic resources, however, are threatened by a rapidly changing world.

As farmers opt to replace their traditional varieties with modern varieties that produce more grain in less time, or they switch from rice to some other crop, their old seeds are often forgotten. And as cities expand, wild rice populations go silently extinct.

"IRRI is extremely concerned about conserving rice genetic diversity and making it available to all who need it," says Mike Jackson, head of IRRI's Genetic Resources Center.

The Rich Heritage of Rice

Although the exact origins of rice have been lost in the mists of time, rice cultivation is believed to have spread from the foothills of the Himalayas southwest into the Indian subcontinent, into Southeast Asia, and eastward into China and Japan.

Farmers only plant two species from the genus *Oryza*: *O. sativa*, originating in Asia and now grown worldwide, and *O. glaberrima*, which is grown in West Africa. More than 20 species of wild rice are scattered across tropical Asia, Africa, and Latin America and the Caribbean. A rich pool of diversity, the wild rice species grow in many different habitats, from sunny open lands to shady forests. Breeders use wild species for traits not found in cultivated rice.

No one really knows how many thousands of rice varieties exist, although some have claimed more than 140,000. "It's not the exact number that is really important," stresses Dr. Jackson. "It's that rice has a broad range of genetic diversity, thanks to the generations of farmers who care-

fully selected the seeds and nurtured plants to fit their unique growing conditions and needs."

Their success is evident in the staggering—yet often subtle—diversity in rice today.

Conserving the Seeds

Since 1962, IRRI has been at the forefront of international collaborative efforts to systematically collect, conserve, characterize, and share traditional rice varieties and wild rice species.

© Cabarrini, Philippines

“IRRI strives to ensure the long-term preservation of rice biodiversity and add value to this biodiversity through research,” explains Dr. Jackson.

The focal point of these efforts is the International Rice Genebank (IRG), which holds in trust the world’s most comprehensive collection of rice genetic resources. The IRG conserves the diversity of the rice gene pool while making seeds available to the world’s scientists in the public and private sectors.

The heritage of generations of rice farmers held in trust at IRRI

Constructed in 1977—and significantly renovated and upgraded in 1994—the IRG has international-standard facilities for medium- and long-term storage of rice seeds at subzero temperatures, a seed-drying room, and screenhouses for multiplying and maintaining wild rice species and low seed stock germplasm.

Although the facilities are not sophisticated as far as genebanks go,

Collecting wild rice

A Glimpse of Rice Diversity

R. Callan, Philippines

they have been ranked among the best in the world, with a recent external review calling the IRG a “model for others.”

More than 100 countries have donated germplasm to the IRG for safe, duplicate storage. The collection now holds more than 90,000 samples of cultivated rice and wild species, most of which are traditional varieties belonging to *O. sativa*. “Two thirds of the samples have been acquired over the years through collecting missions with scientists from national systems or as donations for safety duplication,” explains Dr. Jackson.

The IRG Base Collection, kept at a frigid -20°C , is for long-term storage of several decades. Each sample is stored in two 60-gram vacuum-sealed aluminum cans. The IRG Active Collection is maintained to provide seed samples to requesters and is kept at $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Seeds are stored in hermetically sealed aluminum foil packets. Each sample has about 500 grams of seeds plus several ready-to-go 10-gram packets for immediate exchange.

A backup set of the IRG collection is stored in sealed boxes at the National Seed Storage Laboratory of the United States Department of Agriculture at Fort Collins, Colorado. “This ‘black box’ storage is for safety,” Dr. Jackson stresses. “Only IRRI can open the boxes.”

Managing the IRG requires meticulous attention to an infinite number of details. “We double-check everything,” says genebank manager Pola de Guzman. “Accuracy is extremely important to ensure that we deliver the correct seeds.”

When it comes to rice’s wild relatives, many have special needs. “We really baby them,” says Soccie Almazan, curator of the wild species. “Different species require different cultural practices. *Oryza granulata* and *Oryza meyeriana*, for example, need partial shading and special soils because they grow in forests, whereas

most other species need to be kept soaked because they’re from swamps.”

IRRI maintains these populations and many others in a large screen-house that holds more than 3,000 potted wild rice specimens.

A Complement to Genebanks

Genebanks are not the only way to conserve rice genetic diversity. Although they make seeds readily available for researchers and provide the most secure and cost-effective strategy for long-term preservation, this method is static and halts evolutionary processes.

An important complementary strategy may someday be on-site (*in situ*) conservation, in which wild rice species or populations are preserved in nature and continue to evolve. To date, however, surprisingly little scientific input has gone into on-site design and management of genetic resources.

Today, few wild species are being conserved on-site. Populations of only 10 species have been documented on 18 reserves in Africa and South and Southeast Asia.

On-farm conservation of traditional varieties is a type of *in situ* conservation (see story, p. 44). “By its very nature, on-farm conservation is dynamic, and recognizes that farmers have historically developed and nurtured crop genetic diversity, and will continue to in the future,” says population geneticist Jean-Louis Pham, seconded from the Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération (ORSTOM).

Natural factors, such as mutation and selection, change the makeup of a crop, but so do human selection and management.

Several NGOs in Southeast Asia are sponsoring community projects to conserve the traditional rice varieties, but studies have been limited and many questions remain.

“On-farm conservation must be seen as one of the components of a

“The International Rice Genebank is a treasure trove of rice genes—discovered and undiscovered. Using molecular tools, we now have exciting opportunities to delve into this diversity and make it more accessible to rice science.”

MIKE JACKSON

Head, IRRI Genetic Resources Center

global approach to conserving rice genetic resources that fully exploits both static and dynamic conservation,” Dr. Jackson says.

Collecting Around the World

IRRI and its national partners have been systematically collecting rice genetic resources for years, with large amounts of seeds continuing to flow into the IRG. In 1997, about 6,500 samples were received.

Today, collection efforts focus on countries in which rice diversity is underrepresented in the IRG or is threatened. Lao PDR provides an excellent example. It has gone from an underrepresented country to a super contributor. Since 1995, more than 10,000 samples of cultivated rice have been collected. One set is conserved in Lao PDR and a safety duplicate in the IRG. Lao PDR now represents the second largest component of the IRG collection.

The Institute has also been a catalyst for genetic resources activities in national programs. In 1993, the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation funded a project to accelerate

rice germplasm conservation efforts and to ensure that the broad base of rice biodiversity is secured by 2000 (see story, p. 20).

Sharing Seeds and Information

Many rice varieties safeguarded at IRRI have been restored to their countries of origin when they have been “lost” nationally; these countries included Cambodia, India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka.

Cambodia provides an extreme example. During the time of civil strife, farmers were discouraged from growing deepwater rice, and when they finally could, the seeds were gone. Fortunately, samples had been safely conserved in the IRG. Cambodian farmers are today once again growing these varieties.

“The IRG provides an important safety net for conserving germplasm,” Dr. Jackson says.

Through the IRG, more than 84,000 samples were distributed to researchers in 54 countries between 1993 and 1997.

To facilitate the day-to-day management of rice germplasm and to share this vast body of information, the International Rice Genebank Collection Information System (IRGCIS) was developed. It is available on the World Wide Web through the System-wide Information Network for Genetic Resources (SINGER) project <<http://noc1.cgiar.org>>.

Working Together

Today there are other issues influencing the survival of the diversity of rice and access to these materials, such as the increasing application of biotechnology and the patenting of genes.

Until only a few years ago, plant genetic resources could be collected and used freely by anyone, based on the principle of “common heritage.” The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in June 1992, however, dramatically changed

IRRI's Other Germplasm Specialists

J. Wolters, Philippines
Harvesting a multiplication plot

R. Calarota, Philippines
Pampering wild rice

R. Calarota, Philippines
Sorting seeds

R. Calarota, Philippines
Drying rice for storage

R. Cabrera, Philippines

Using molecular biology to reveal diversity at the gene level

the way the world views biodiversity. One of the conference's most important outcomes was the birth of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), which came into force in December 1993. Now ratified by more than 170 nations, the CBD provides a legal framework for conserving and using biodiversity, with nations having sovereign rights over their biodiversity.

The CBD, combined with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations' (FAO) Global Plan of Action that was adopted in Leipzig in June 1996, signals global commitment for fostering sustainable development and equitable sharing of the benefits of conserving and using genetic resources.

"The Global Plan of Action will guide genetic resources activities and

funding opportunities for at least the next decade," says Dr. Jackson.

To safeguard the genetic resources held in trust for the world, IRRI and the other CGIAR centers placed their pre-CBD germplasm collections under the auspices of FAO in 1994. When sharing genetic resources, a material transfer agreement is used to assure the continued free availability of the materials and of genes derived directly from them.

The Future Is Today

Over the years, scientists from IRRI and national systems have worked together to collect, conserve, and study rice genetic resources. And they will continue to in the future.

Recent developments in molecular biology, and particularly genome research, will significantly increase scientists' understanding of rice diversity. In a project funded by the Government of the United Kingdom, IRRI researchers have been collaborating with scientists at The University of Birmingham and the John Innes Centre in using molecular markers to assess diversity and to identify duplicate accessions in the IRG collection.

"We have made good progress and now feel confident to use these techniques routinely to study the germplasm collection," says Dr. Jackson. "We believe that these tools will help us unlock this diversity. It's exciting to imagine what we may do in just a few years' time."

The scientist predicts that rice researchers will be using molecular data from other crops, such as for drought tolerance in sorghum, to search for this trait in the rice germplasm collection.

"Ultimately, one can think of the IRG as simply lots of seed samples," says Dr. Jackson. "Or one can think of it as the genetic heritage of generations of rice farmers. That's what IRRI is here to conserve—and to use wisely—to benefit farmers in the future." ■

Beyond Rice

Wide Crosses Broaden the Gene Pool

Using sophisticated techniques to get around nature's roadblocks, scientists are stretching the gene pool—and their imaginations—to make crosses between cultivated rice and its wild relatives. Their goal? To create rice plants that yield bountifully and stand up to harsh environments and pests.

Although extraordinarily diverse, the cultivated rice gene pool simply doesn't possess some of the building blocks needed to make better varieties. So scientists have been tapping into rice's rugged wild relatives for the traits they want—with impressive results.

"We are striving for the best of both parents in one rice plant: high yields from the cultivated rice and the ability to thrive in harsh environments and survive pest attacks—without pesticides—from the wild rice," says IRRI plant breeder Darshan Brar.

Nature, however, has thrown several roadblocks in scientists' paths while they try to make crosses between these distantly related plants through a process called wide hybridization. Getting around these blockages has taken scientists years of painstaking work and biotechnological wizardry. The trick has been to coax these incompatible parents into producing viable offspring.

Seeking Solutions

Farmers grow only two rice species: *Oryza sativa*, which originated in Asia and is now planted worldwide, and *O. glaberrima*, from West Africa. The genus *Oryza* also has more than 20 wild species, sprinkled throughout tropical Asia, Australia, Africa, and Latin America and the Caribbean.

The cultivated and wild species in *Oryza* and the related genera in the tribe *Oryzaceae* comprise the biodiversity of the rice gene pool. Like rings around the primary gene pool of cultivated rice, the secondary and tertiary gene pools have progressively more dissimilarities with rice, but they are still more similar than unrelated species. And

therein lies the secret for improving cultivated rice.

Wild Relatives Donate Diversity

Wild rice species are a rich reservoir of biodiversity, developed over centuries of surviving pest attacks and extreme environments. They also serve as new sources for cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS)—an unusual condition in which plants produce no functional pollen—needed in hybrid rice.

"The role of wild relatives in crop improvement is critical," explains Gurdev Khush, who has been developing improved rice for more than 30 years as IRRI's principal plant breeder.

Some crosses, however, are simpler to make than others. The easiest are the relatively "narrow" crosses among species with similar genetic backgrounds, or genomes. In the 1970s, IRRI scientists began producing a series of hybrids between *O. sativa* and its closest wild relatives, those with the AA genome, by making direct crosses using conventional plant breeding methods.

But when it comes to wide crosses between cultivated rice and a relative belonging to one of the

eight genomes other than the AA, such as BB or CCDD, a perplexing thing happens if left to nature: the seeds are nearly always aborted—meaning no hybrids.

Science to the Rescue

If scientists intervene, however, they can save the embryos from the dying seeds through a process called embryo rescue. Demonstrating the delicate surgery, Dr. Brar looks through a microscope, and carefully cuts the tiny embryo from the deteriorating seed and places it in a test tube. Nourished on a special nutrient medium, the embryo will grow into a rice plant with the traits of both parents.

These hybrids are then crossed and recrossed with the rice parent until they become fertile plants with the normal 24 chromosomes of rice plus a spare—a desirable chromosome segment from the wild species. Using molecular markers, scientists can easily determine whether the "alien" gene was incorporated—and where—on the chromosome.

"Biotechnology takes the guesswork out of breeding and allows us to monitor the transfer of alien ge-

B. Lu, Cambodia

Sampling wild rice – before it disappears

netic material that is otherwise difficult through conventional breeding approaches,” explains Dr. Brar.

Widespread Successes

Building multiple disease and insect resistances into modern varieties has become one of the main strategies for improving productivity and yield stability—and lessening the use of chemical inputs. Conventional breeding approaches, however, haven’t been very successful in easing the problems of too much heat, drought, or soils that are too salty. Scientists are exploring what wild species have to offer their cultivated cousins to combat these stresses.

One of the first transfusions of wild rice genes into rice occurred in the 1970s at IRRI for resistance to grassy stunt virus. Of the 6,700 samples screened, only one was found highly resistant. “That population of *O. nivara* from Uttar Pradesh, India, has never been found again, making those seeds truly priceless,” says Dr. Khush, who led the efforts. Through conventional methods, the resistance was bred into modern varieties, reducing disease incidence on millions of hectares.

Rice scientists have since made many impressive accomplishments using wide crosses. Genes for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH), bacterial blight, blast, and tungro have been identified in wild rice and transferred into promising breeding lines. Using several of these resistance genes for a particular pest in a “pyramid” improves durability against the evolving pests. Genes with a broad spectrum of resistance for BPH and bacterial blight have been transferred into promising breeding lines from different wild species; four BPH-resistant lines have been released as varieties in Vietnam.

Wide-cross progenies are being evaluated for resistance to yellow

stem borer and sheath blight, and tolerance for submergence and acid sulfate soils. “The cultivated rice gene pool has limited variability for these pests and stresses, so wide hybridization and genetic engineering are good options,” says Dr. Brar.

A hybrid was recently produced from a wide cross between cultivated rice and a member of the tertiary gene pool, *Porteresia coarctata*—a hardy grass that grows in salty coastal areas of eastern India and Bangladesh. This extremely promising hybrid will be used to create rice varieties that thrive in salty soils, both in coastal areas and in irrigation-damaged soils.

Wild rice is also making contributions to the world of hybrid rice. Most commercial hybrids are based on the “wild abortive” CMS source from *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*. To prevent the possibility of widespread genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects, scientists have been developing diverse CMS lines with the cytoplasm of AA genome wild species *O. rufipogon* and *O. glumaepatula*. These lines are now being used in breeding programs.

Helping Poor Farmers

In a project sponsored by the Japanese Government, IRRI scientists and those at the West Africa Rice Development Association are crossing the high-yielding Asian rice species *O. sativa* with the African species *O. glaberrima*, which has outstanding weed competitiveness, drought tolerance, nematode resistance, and tolerance for iron and aluminum toxicities. The goal is to increase diversity—and raise productivity in both by incorporating useful genes from one into the other. “We are optimistic about this approach,” Dr. Brar says.

Wide crosses may someday be critical for taking advantage of the natural phenomenon of apomixis,

“We’re moving genes from the jungles and swamps into the rice gene pool to increase its diversity. If left to nature, this rich reservoir would go untapped.”

DARSHAN BRAR
IRRI Plant Breeder

R. Cabrera, Philippines

which is asexual reproduction through seed that results in offspring that are exactly the same as the mother plant. Dr. Brar and his colleagues are tediously examining young ovules from selected species in the secondary and tertiary *Oryza* gene pools in an attempt to find apomictic strains. If these are identified, wide hybridization will be used to transfer the genes to cultivated rice. The implications are great: apomixis will enable poor farmers to save and plant their own hybrid seeds.

Advances in biotechnology and genetic engineering are constantly increasing scientists’ abilities to use the genes of wild relatives to improve commercial rice. “With wide hybridization, we can more fully appreciate and use the Earth’s biodiversity,” Dr. Brar says.

Ultimately, the only limit to creating successful new plants may be a scientist’s imagination. ■

Teaching People to Save Seeds

Bhutan has embarked on an ambitious plan to collect traditional varieties of rice and other crops before modern varieties cause significant genetic erosion.

G. Hettel, Bhutan

The Kingdom of Bhutan is a landlocked country wedged between China and India and sealed off by its mountains. It is rich in culture, architecture, and biodiversity—particularly of rice.

In a race against time, Bhutan and other countries around the world are preserving traditional crop varieties and wild species before they disappear forever. In a project sponsored by the Swiss Agency for Development and Co-

operation (SDC), IRRI is supporting collecting and training efforts in partnership with national agricultural research systems.

Farmers Sharing Knowledge

In the remote eastern *dzongkhag* (district) of Tashigang in Manthung village, farmer Dechen Yudon watches closely as extension worker Karma Tenzin strips the hairy grains from a rice panicle and spreads them on a germplasm collection information form.

“We call this variety ‘Pure Mebra’ because of its whitish covering,” Ms. Yudon says in her local Sharchop dialect. Her family has grown this variety for generations because it thrives without much water and fertilizer. The grain is used for food, beverages, and religious offerings.

As Mr. Tenzin meticulously records the farmer’s information for two more traditional rice varieties, eight other extension workers from the region listen closely, some

G. Hettel, Bhutan

carefully taking their own notes. A Manthung village chief has accompanied the group to encourage farmers to cooperate. Without his presence, for example, Ms. Yudon would normally never talk with a group of strangers.

Three other groups of extension personnel are also doing field practicals this day as part of a week-long course on collecting and conserving rice germplasm. When the course is finished, the extension workers will return to their dzongkhags to collect in places never before sampled.

Training Key to Preserving Rice

The intensive course, held in October 1997 in the remote mountain town of Khangma, Tashigang, was the first for any discipline in eastern Bhutan—for good reason. Reaching the site requires a 2-day drive on narrow and winding mountain roads.

Taught by germplasm specialists Genoveva Loresto and Bao-Rong Lu, both from the IRRI Genetic Resources Center, the course provides participants with an awareness of the value of germplasm conservation and use. They learn about the rice plant and its gene pool, and how to differentiate varieties in farmers' fields and identify wild species in their natural habitats. They also study proper methods in sampling and handling seeds, and gathering and managing information about the samples.

To date, about 380 samples from Bhutan are conserved in the International Rice Genebank (IRG) at IRRI, with nearly half of these collected in 1996 thanks to the SDC project. The IRRI scientists are optimistic that several hundred traditional varieties will be collect-

Learning from the expert—
a Bhutanese farmer

ed from along the region's steep mountain slopes.

Collecting Around the World

The clock is ticking in a race against time to collect and preserve cultivated rice and wild species before they disappear forever. The 5-year SDC project, "Safeguarding and Preservation of the Biodiversity of the Rice Gene Pool," started in 1994. The project has a challenging focus: it involves field collection of germplasm, on-farm conservation, national staff training, and genebank facility development.

Considering the difficulties and time required to collect seeds in remote areas—such as in the mountains of eastern Bhutan or the swamps and small lakes of Cambodia and Lao PDR—the most practical scenario is to involve national extension service personnel.

"We know our areas and farmers very well," says Galay Phuntsho, a short-course graduate and extension worker from Hastinapur, Samdrup Jongkhar. "We can sample seeds while we are doing our routine activities, and we can go to key locations that are sometimes restricted to foreign collectors."

The SDC project has been meeting a pressing need to train plant genetic resources workers and extension personnel in aspects of conservation and field collection.

As more and more modern varieties make their way into farmers' fields, low-yielding traditional varieties of the two cultivated *Oryza* species (*O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima*) are being abandoned. Alarming extinction is occurring in the more than 20 wild *Oryza* species as fragile habitats are destroyed, especially in areas undergoing rapid economic development.

"We stand to lose irreplaceable genetic resources contained in these two gene pools," says Dr. Lu.

A. Rice, Lao PDR
Lao PDR germplasm coordinator collecting upland rice

Committed Government

Improved varieties of rice, maize, wheat, barley, and other crops are only now being introduced in Bhutan, so not many traditional varieties have been lost—yet. More than 90 percent of the country's rice land is still planted to diverse traditional varieties.

According to Ganesh Chettri, program coordinator for field crops research of the Renewable Natural Resources Center in western Bhutan, the SDC/IRRI-sponsored collection and training efforts are extremely timely. "Our crop biodiversity is, for the most part, still intact," he says. "Our cautious

A. Ammayao-Hettel, Bhutan

G. Hettel, Bhutan

farmers do not adopt new varieties too rapidly." Like the Yudon family in Manthung, most farmers still grow several traditional rice varieties in the same field because they are well adapted to their conditions and have good eating quality.

Rice germplasm collecting is actually just the first step in the Royal Government of Bhutan's activities to conserve natural resources. The Agro-Biodiversity Program also calls for germplasm collection of maize, dryland wheat, buckwheat, mustard, vegetables, and legumes.

Project on Target

Now in its fourth year, the SDC project is well on track. Project participants have so far gathered 15,160 previously uncollected unique seed samples: 14,018 samples of traditional rice varieties and 1,142 of wild species from the targeted countries.

Ultimately, all participating countries will control their own base collections of traditional varieties and wild species collected through this project. Countries with functional genebanks are already doing so.

"Establishing a long-term storage facility to house our base collections for rice and other crops is a priority of the Ministry of Agricul-

"We asked the IRRI team to return to train our extension people in eastern Bhutan so that they, too, would be aware of the importance of genetic resources—not just for rice, but for all crops."

T.B. CHETTRI
Renewable Natural Resources
Center, Bhutan

ture as part of the Agro-Biodiversity Program," says Ganesh Chettri.

IRRI is providing duplicate storage for the base collections of all these materials. "This will assure that breeders of the future in all countries will have a wealth of genetic resources to draw upon," says Dr. Lu.

The IRRI team has trained about 215 national plant genetic resources workers and extension personnel in collecting activities in Cambodia, Lao PDR, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mozambique, Myanmar,

Farmers explaining the qualities of local rice varieties

Nepal, and Vietnam—as well as Bhutan.

More than 60 percent of the accessions have come from Lao PDR where Dr. Seepana Appa Rao spends much of his time collecting and conducting training courses as part of the SDC project work. “Just as in Bhutan, Lao PDR has large areas that rice germplasm collectors have never visited,” says Dr. Rao.

Trainee Enthusiasm

The Bhutanese trainees reflect the enthusiasm that Ms. Loresto and Dr. Lu have witnessed in most of the 20 countries in Asia and Africa

in which they have conducted the short course.

Tashi Tshering, an assistant extension officer from Khaling, Tashigang, provides a good example. A participant in the 1996 short course, he returned to the 1997 course in Khangma as a trainer to relay his collecting experiences. His main advice: “Collect in areas where the farmers know you, or travel with someone they know. Nothing hinders collecting work more than farmers hesitating to cooperate with strangers.”

The Khangma trainees in Bhutan were anxious to try out their

new skills once they returned to their home dzongkhags. “Before this course, I didn’t know anything about collecting germplasm from farmers’ fields and actually never gave it any thought,” says Haka Dukpa, an extension officer from Duksum, Tashigang. “I am now confident that I can do the job.”

Adds Ms. Yeshey, a research assistant in soil and water management at Khangma: “It is important to preserve the crop germplasm in our country before it is lost forever. I now have the skills to assist in this effort when visiting farmers in my region.” ■

Delivering Diversity to the Field

How many parents are enough? For humans, most would say two are plenty. But in the case of rice and other crops, more than two often provide distinct advantages—such as high yields and the ability to withstand insects and diseases.

Take IR36, one of the all-time favorite modern, or improved, rice varieties. It has 35 parents. IR72 has 46. All these parents are traditional varieties, carefully grown and selected over the centuries by farmers. A few wild rice plants have also been parents. IR36, for example, has *Oryza nivara*, a wild relative of rice, in its ancestry. With the advent of biotechnology and genetic engineering, “parents”—more accurately gene donors—can even be of the nontraditional type: soybean and bacteria.

Traditional varieties, sometimes called landraces or local or farmer varieties, form the foundation on which to build better rice plants. “We couldn’t develop modern varieties without them,” says Gurdev Khush, IRRI’s principal plant breeder and head of the Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division.

Balancing the Choices

Farmers continue to grow many different rice varieties. But the number of traditional varieties being planted has shrunk, with a few productive and relatively uniform high-yielding varieties dominating the rice landscape.

This widespread planting of modern rice varieties, particularly in the irrigated ecosystem, has kept the world’s ballooning masses fed. But these varieties have also increased the danger of genetic vulnerability to major disease or insect pest outbreaks.

The success of rice breeding is exemplified by the case of IR36, which was eventually grown on more than 11 million hectares—the most widely grown variety ever. Its popularity was mainly because of its resistance to several insect pests and diseases, particularly brown planthopper and grassy stunt virus. But too much of a good thing isn’t necessarily desirable. Emergence of a new pest can wipe out large areas of any widely grown variety.

“IRRI breeders have been sensitive about increasing genetic diversity in their breeding programs, and ultimately in rice varieties on the farm,” Dr. Khush points out.

Rice breeders are more conscious than ever about developing varieties that reflect the richness of the gene pool. Using diverse parents from around the world, scientists are working to slow genetic erosion—and give farmers more options.

Using the Bounty of Diversity

Whether subsistence or commercial, irrigated or rainfed, all rice farmers need genetic diversity in their rice as the basis for a healthy crop. Diverse parentage among many modern varieties helps lessen the likelihood of an epidemic in intensive agricultural systems—like that of tropical irrigated rice. Genetic diversity also helps prevent minor pests from evolving into major ones, and lessens devastation from bad weather.

G. Hettel, Philippines

The origin of 1,709 modern varieties in Asia can be traced to 11,592 traditional varieties, and the pedigrees of IRRI breeding lines and varieties until 1994 can be traced to hundreds of traditional varieties from most Asian countries. Hardy wild species, well adapted to extreme environments and capable

Selecting seeds for the next year's rice crop

R. Kariadinata - Madagascar

of warding off pests and diseases, have also made important contributions.

“We have been deliberately broadening the genetic base by adding never-before-used traditional varieties to the breeding program each year,” Dr. Khush explains.

A study of the pedigrees of modern rice varieties made by Dr. Robert Evenson, an economist at Yale University, reveals evidence of

these efforts. About 1,700 varieties from more than 100 breeding programs have been released since the early 1960s, with about 75 released per year since 1980. Through the popular “one parent from IRRI, one from the national system” approach to breeding rice, the average number of traditional varieties in the parentage of released varieties has increased from three in the late 1960s to eight today—although some have many more. About 70 percent of these traditional varieties were brought into the genealogies of national varieties through an IRRI ancestor, Dr. Evenson reports.

Although IRRI stopped releasing varieties itself in 1975, the Government of the Philippines continued releasing IRRI breeding lines with the IR designation until 1988. Nevertheless, IRRI has remained important in influencing which rice varieties get into farmers’ fields, primarily through its breeding lines. Between 1966 and 1970, IRRI made 25 percent of all crosses leading to

Rice diversity decreases when farmers choose to plant other crops

varieties; it now makes 12 percent. Traditional varieties incorporated in new IRRI breeding lines have steadily increased from the early 1960s to the early 1990s, and the genetic relationship among lines bred at IRRI is actually declining.

In other work, scientists at the Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice) found the genetic diversity of IRRI-bred materials to be comparable with those developed by the Philippine’s Bureau of Plant Industry and the University of the Philippines Los Baños. This study also reveals that IRRI’s irrigated and rainfed lowland varieties and lines represent two distinct sets of genetic diversity.

A dramatic change will occur in irrigated rice fields when the new plant type varieties are released in a few years. With a radically different genetic composition than today’s best modern varieties, these plants

Increasing diversity in the seed: the number of traditional varieties used as parents to develop IRRI varieties and lines

will bring new diversity into farmers' fields (see story, p. 34).

Understanding Diversity

Intensive cultivation of modern varieties, plus fertilizers and irrigation, has increased the world's food supply and lowered the real price of food. But these advances have come at a cost: lost genetic diversity.

"No one can dispute that modern varieties, because of their superior yields, have displaced many traditional varieties—particularly in irrigated areas," Dr. Khush says.

The real question, which may never be answered, is how much genetic erosion has occurred.

"We really don't know what the genetic diversity was like prior to modern varieties being introduced," says population geneticist Jean-Louis Pham, seconded to IRRI from the Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération (ORSTOM).

Genes are lost when populations of plants disappear because farmers adopt modern varieties, clear land, change farming systems (such as in the uplands when they stop planting rice to grow maize or vegetables), or change cultural practices. In Asia, populations of wild species are commonly bulldozed into extinction as cities grow.

The adoption of modern varieties, however, has been uneven across rice ecosystems. If a direct relationship is assumed between the degree of adoption and the level of genetic erosion, then the highest erosion has occurred in the irrigated ecosystem and the lowest in the upland and flood-prone ones. The rainfed lowland ecosystem is somewhere in between.

Although traditional varieties are a rich source of genetic diversity and their loss is regrettable, maintaining diversity on farms is not a matter of planting only traditional

"Our ability to feed the billions of people who depend on rice is pivotal on the continuous supply of high-yielding and genetically diverse rice varieties. We should encourage diversity in farmers' fields by providing varieties with differences in growth duration, grain quality, disease and insect resistance, and abiotic stress tolerance."

DR. GURDEV KHUSH
Principal Plant Breeder and
World Food Prize Laureate

varieties. "Growing only one or two farmers' varieties over large areas is similar to planting one or two modern varieties," Dr. Pham says. "Diversity depends on the number and genetic similarity of varieties grown in an area—not whether they are traditional varieties or modern varieties."

Traditional varieties are not necessarily more diverse than modern varieties. Modern varieties simply have genes from more parents than do traditional varieties.

Respecting Farmers' Decisions

Farmers and scientists should both be applauded for their remarkable accomplishments in developing rice varieties. Modern and traditional varieties need to be viewed as complementary—not competitive. Each has its place in farmers' fields.

"Farmers don't necessarily discard their traditional varieties, they add modern varieties to their pool," says Dr. Pham.

The two types can—and do—coexist. Farmers in the rainfed lowlands grow both modern and traditional varieties, sometimes in alternating seasons. This practice, however, is less common in irrigated areas.

"This scheme makes a lot of sense because farmers want high yields and rice that tastes good, and generally you don't get both from the same variety," says IRRI socio-cultural anthropologist Steve Morin.

"Farmers often see distinct advantages in modern varieties for lessening risks," says Dr. Pham. The biggest is that modern varieties are shorter in duration, which allows farmers to have enough time to grow another crop or to cope with erratic rains. But they hold on to their traditional varieties for their own families to eat because they taste "right" or because they are particularly well suited to their areas.

"Whether farmers use modern or traditional varieties or both, we need to give them options," Dr. Morin stresses. "They will reject modern varieties if they do not perform at least as well as their traditional ones, and they will hold on to traditional varieties they like." ■

Partners in Rainfed Rice Breeding

Farmers and scientists are working in partnership to develop rainfed rice varieties that are appropriate for local conditions in eastern India. Scientists are listening to what farmers want in their rice—and then creating new plants from the ground up: together.

It was already late June and farmers in the village of Mungishpur, Faizabad District of Uttar Pradesh, were still waiting for the first drop of rain. Rice seedlings, ready for transplanting but quickly turning yellow, were piled high under a tree.

“If we don’t have rain during the next few days, it’ll soon be too late to transplant the seedlings,” says Laxmi, one of the millions of women farmers in eastern India who depend on rain to grow rice. “If we have no rice crop, my family will go hungry, and we won’t have rice straw to feed our livestock.”

Farmers in eastern India still rely on their tried and true traditional rice varieties for survival. They have accepted only a handful of modern rainfed varieties over the years. These traditional plants don’t produce much grain—only 1.2 to 1.5 tons per hectare—but they can be relied on to at least yield some rice no matter what the weather.

Rice scientists decided to investigate why farmers opt for their own varieties over new ones. In the process, they’re developing a new rice breeding methodology for the heterogeneous rainfed environment that is turning farmers into true

partners—which will ultimately help them to raise themselves out of poverty.

Getting the Answers

In the harsh, extremely variable climate of eastern India—where rainfed lowland fields may produce a good crop one season and then be flooded or burned by drought the next, and upland fields are always precarious—plant breeders have struggled to develop modern rice varieties that farmers will adopt.

“The centralized breeding approaches commonly used in the uniform irrigated ecosystem were not designed to cope with the heterogeneity in the rainfed upland and lowland areas,” explains upland rice breeder Brigitte Courtois, seconded to IRRI from the Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement, département des cultures annuelles (CIRAD-CA).

Scientists and farmers learn together

V.P. Singh, India

As a consequence, modern rainfed varieties are often acceptable on average—but to an individual farmer there is no such thing as an average condition. “A farmer usually only cares about his or her own farm,” says IRRI agronomist Virendra Pal Singh.

With the world’s largest concentration of rainfed rice—nearly 20 million hectares—eastern India is the perfect place for testing a new methodology in a multitude of unique rice-based systems and cultural and economic diversity. And with 450 million people depending on rainfed rice for their livelihoods, the crop is of utmost importance.

Old Concept, New Twist

The idea of scientists working closely with farmers is certainly not new. Many conscientious plant breeders routinely seek out farmers’ opinions to ensure that their varieties are grounded in reality. But they seldom use a systematic approach, and rarely are results formally analyzed. The conclusions reached may be erroneous because of poor sampling or unconscious biases of the questions.

Participatory plant breeding stresses the importance of preserving genetic diversity and providing farmers with a basket of choices. Few participatory plant breeding attempts to date have involved farmers in the core of the work.

According to R.K. Singh, IRRI liaison scientist to India and plant breeder, two general reasons are behind the poor adoption of varieties: the modern varieties are good, but farmers can’t obtain them, or the modern varieties have no comparative advantage or are even inferior to traditional varieties. In the second case, breeders must modify the way they are working. Selection criteria of breeders and farmers may differ, but both are valuable. “The

list of criteria is not the only element to be considered; the ranking of the criteria may also vary for each group,” he says.

Breeders, for example, may consider things farmers generally do not detect, such as resistance to nematodes, and farmers may value traits not considered important by breeders, such as straw production, competitiveness with weeds, or specific grain quality traits. In this complex mix, economic status, social class, ethnicity, and degree of market integration can all make differences, too.

“Commercial farmers often want high yields, good grain quality, and a nice golden color,” explains A.S. Sastri, associate director of research at the Indira Gandhi Agricultural University in Raipur and project collaborator. “But for small-scale farmers, straw yield is often extremely important.”

In a project carried out through the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium, farmers have been choosing the rice they like best from promising breeding lines.

Women’s knowledge must be sought when developing new varieties

“The idea behind participatory varietal selection is that farmers tell us their opinions when varieties are still being molded—not after they’re released and nothing can be done,” says Surapong Sarkarung, an IRRI rainfed lowland rice breeder stationed in Thailand.

During the past 3 years, four rainfed lowland rice varieties developed through this process were released in eastern India with the farmer stamp of approval. Although this was encouraging, Dr. Sarkarung and his collaborators realized that screening lines that are nearly ready for release still brings farmers’ views into the process a little too late.

“Farmers need to be full partners in developing rainfed varieties from the beginning,” advocates Dr. Sarkarung.

So scientists decided to develop, test, and perfect a methodology for participatory plant breeding of rainfed upland and lowland rice—with farmers.

“Scientists need to listen to what women say they prefer in rice varieties. Including their opinions in plant breeding objectives will lead to higher acceptance of new varieties for rainfed conditions.”

THELMA PARIS
IRRI Social Scientist

Working Together

Funded by the International Development Research Centre of Canada, the Participatory Plant Breeding Project has brought together plant breeders, anthropologists, and agricultural economists from six agricultural research institutions in eastern India and IRRI in addition to extension workers from local Farm Science Centers and farmers in an effort to tackle the challenge of developing a participatory plant breeding approach for rainfed rice.

“Our main goal is to determine whether involving farmers in the breeding process of modern varieties improves the adoption rate,” Dr. Courtois says. “We’re also interested in examining how farmer participation influences crop biodiversity.”

To get started, three sites were chosen for the rainfed lowland ecosystem: Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, which suffers from drought; Masodha, Uttar Pradesh, with an environment prone to drought and shallow submergence; and Cuttack, Orissa, which is a coastal submergence-prone area. For the upland ecosystem, Hazaribagh, Bihar, was

selected. At each site, two or three villages were chosen and interested farmers—both men and women—selected.

Emphasis on Women

As a part of the research, scientists are developing methods for incorporating male and female farmers’ knowledge of traditional cultivars and their criteria for selecting varieties into plant breeding strategies. Findings will be fed into the CGIAR’s Systemwide Initiative on Participatory Research and Gender Analysis.

“Despite the significant roles women play in rice farming, they often are not culturally perceived as farmers,” says Thelma Paris, an IRRI social scientist specializing in gender issues, who is working with women farmers.

Involving women in this research is an absolute must. In eastern India, poor women provide much of the labor for producing the rice crop. Women transplant, weed, harvest, thresh—and select and save the seeds.

And yet, when new rice seeds are introduced and tested in farmers’ fields, somehow the women farmers often become “invisible” or are ignored in the research agenda.

Based on initial interviews, the importance of rice as fodder was revealed. “To these women, high yield is not the only trait that matters in their complicated and risky farming systems,” adds Ms. Paris.

A Promising Process

“We started at square one by reexamining with farmers what they value in rice varieties, and why they do—and do not—grow specific ones,” explains Dr. Courtois. Test materials were then defined, and farmers given different rice lines to grow on their own land and in a

community demonstration plot. Breeders grew the same set of lines on their station. Then both farmers and breeders selected those they liked best at the different sites—and gave their opinions why.

“We want to be able to separate the effects of decentralization of the breeding work in farmers’ fields from the effects of farmer participation in the process,” explains Dr. Courtois.

With the first season’s work completed in 1997, both progress and farmers’ reactions have been positive. “The interactions among scientists and farmers, and among the farmers themselves are valuable,” Dr. Courtois says.

During the next two years, participatory varietal selection and participatory breeding will continue, and seeds will be produced. It is anticipated that materials selected by farmers using their own criteria will have a much greater chance of being accepted.

Breeders are also introducing stress tolerance genes into some popular eastern Indian varieties using molecular marker technology. This material will become part of the next generation of materials to be tested in the project.

Once rice lines are identified, scientists will have to grapple with a different problem: how to scale up what are extremely localized experiences.

“We need to develop a methodology that permits a reasonable area at the lowest cost while satisfying local needs,” Dr. Courtois says.

Although it’s still too soon to judge the success of the approach, Dr. V.P. Singh is optimistic. “There’s definitely increased awareness among the participating farmers and their neighbors about their roles in developing varieties suited to their own needs. And this is encouraging.” ■

Cultural Diversity Through Genetic Diversity

GELIA T. CASTILLO

In *The Idea of Biodiversity*, David Takacs says that for him, the word biodiversity signals a cultural phenomenon. This interpretation would certainly not be the expected observation made by rice scientists. When they exchange rice seeds for evaluation, they look at their biological or genetic qualities—not their cultural significance.

In espousing a people orientation in our goal of achieving food security, poverty alleviation, and environmental sustainability, we find in the 23-year-old International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER) an ideal-type network. INGER is composed of rice scientists: about a thousand from the national agricultural research systems of 95 rice-growing countries and from four international agricultural research centers (IITA, WARDA, CIAT, and IRRI).

There are social and cultural values embedded in this network, although its name suggests very genetic- and germplasm-centered activities. Beyond the genetic lingo of B2161C-MR-57 and P901-22-11, people actually lie at its heart. The network fosters participation in a new culture of cooperation, consciousness of sharing, and exchange—not only of breeding lines, but of information, insights, and experiences toward a shared objective.

Cultural Dividends

From 1975 to 1997, more than 42,000 breeding lines and varieties have been

exchanged and evaluated globally. Germplasm has moved from one continent to another and among countries within a continent. Sometimes countries had no diplomatic relations; INGER's political neutrality helped them to overcome this.

INGER provides an opportunity for every country, large or small, rich or poor, to be a donor of valuable genetic materials that could help another country—even one that is “not a friend” or one that is richer. An unspoken norm exists that those who have more will give more.

Varieties directly released in different countries through INGER and those varieties with parents donated by other countries are the epitome of international public goods in both spirit and substance. They actually benefit real people.

Genetic diversity is helping to ensure that cultural diversity will endure. Grain quality, for example, must match consumer preferences, which are truly cultural preferences. This is very much in the United Nations' vision of human development, defined as the “process of enabling people to have wider choices.”

Rice seeds share a common food value and “speak” a common language that transcends politics, geography, and culture. In Africa, for instance, INGER helped to break the barrier in rice science between English-speaking and French-speaking countries.

Unique Culture of Reciprocity

In traditional societies and subsistence farm households, food security is not just a matter of food production but also of investing and maintaining social relations.

At the family, kinship, and community levels, the exchange and sharing of seeds and planting materials take place on a very reciprocal basis. Seeds are also given as gifts. In this reciprocal relationship, the basis of exchange is not money, but trust and mutuality of benefit.

INGER is a shining example of how seemingly “romantic” notions of interdependence, exchange, and sharing work in real life. In this network, no country is too poor to give and no one is too rich to receive. This is a philosophy that promotes a unique culture of reciprocity at the global level that is improved by the tools of science.

INGER is a beautiful illustration of humanity working together for our common future in a world filled with social conflicts, tribal wars, and fierce competition over the control of natural resources. We must continue to share even as countries declare national sovereignty over plant genetic resources. After all, rice is life. ■

Dr. Castillo is emeritus professor of rural sociology at the University of the Philippines Los Baños and an early pioneer in the concept of participatory development. She is the author of *All in a Grain of Rice*, and has served on the boards of trustees of IDRC, CIP, ISNAR, ICRAF, and IPGRI.

**THE
GEOMETRY
OF
RICE**

A photograph of a person working in a flat, brown rice field. The person is wearing a white shirt and dark pants, and is using a long-handled tool, possibly a rake or a similar agricultural implement, to work the soil. The field is a uniform reddish-brown color, and the person's shadow is cast on the ground to their left. The background shows faint, repetitive patterns of the field, suggesting a large-scale agricultural operation.

The profile of the rice landscape is diverse, going from soft to hard, flat to hilly, curvy to straight. In some places, it blends harmoniously with nature, in others it's overpowering. Fields are terraced onto steep mountainsides, flow with the contours of valleys, and slice their own lines across flatlands.

Rice fields and the areas around them are home to hundreds of species. Some are hidden in the soil, others buzz through the air.

Agriculture and nature can coexist if systems are designed with balance and harmony in mind. The research done today will shape the rice fields of tomorrow—and the geometry of the landscape. ■

Irrigated Rice

Dr. Kenrick, Philippines

Irrigated rice is the keystone to global food security. About 80 million hectares of rice land are irrigated, producing about 75 percent of the world's rice. Yields vary from 3 to 9 tons per hectare and average 5 tons per hectare. Irrigated rice farmers generally use more purchased inputs than rainfed farmers.

Modern varieties for irrigated fields are short in duration and nitrogen responsive, and have multiple resistance to insect pests and diseases and some tolerance for adverse soils.

New Plant Type on Track

There's good news on the new plant type front. In a Herculean effort that began in 1989, IRRI plant breeders have been building a better rice plant with a new genetic background (tropical japonica), a new structure, increased suitability for direct seeding, and a yield potential that's targeted at 20-25 percent more than today's best high-yielding indica modern varieties.

In 1996, scientists became concerned about the new plant type's less than ideal grain filling. It was preventing the plants from expressing their true yield potential.

Breeders and physiologists quickly overcame these weaknesses by incorporating genes from indica parents with robust grain-filling traits. These new parents have further increased the genetic base of the new plant type.

During the 1997 wet season, nine of the new plant type lines had a grain-filling rate of more than 60 percent—four had

more than 70 percent. In comparison, 64 percent of the grains filled for IR72, the current highest yielding variety.

"We are optimistic that we are overcoming this obstacle," says Gurdev Khush, IRRI's principal plant breeder.

Four of the new plant type lines outyielded IR72 in the 1997 wet season, and numerous breeding lines from crosses between new plant type lines and improved indica lines were evaluated, with some appearing very promising.

Breeders have also already built in resistance to several insect pests and diseases.

"Within the next three years, we hope to make the final improvements and test the lines extensively before distributing them to national programs," says Dr. Khush. "By 2005, this new rice should be available for farmers to grow in their fields."

The next-step activities will be to test the lines under different establishment methods (transplanting and direct seeding), continue studying the causes of low grain filling, and work on improving grain quality.

Ensuring Nutrients for Increased Yields

By 2025, farmers must produce an estimated 590 million tons of rice. This means increasing irrigated rice yield from 5 tons per hectare in 1995 to 7.9 tons per hectare in 2025—a 1.5 percent increase per year. But does this also mean increasing inputs at a similar rate?

IRRI scientists have shown that nitrogen (N) efficiency can be increased by 50 percent in farmers' fields by improving the congruence between N supply and plant N demand. But the other major elements, phosphorus (P) and potassium (K), will need to be increased to maintain a healthy balance of nutrients. "Without this balance, some nutrients would be overused," says Achim Dobermann, soil nutrient specialist.

To determine what it will take to increase yields to keep up with demand, scientists have developed a simulation model for forecasting NPK fertilizer use and nutrient balances for irrigated rice lands in Asia.

If the NPK fertilizer use is balanced with high nutrient use efficiency, the findings are surprising: to get an average yield of almost 8 tons per hectare in 2025, farmers would have to increase the N and P applied by 55 percent. But for K, the level would have to increase 600 percent over current levels, bringing fertilizer applications to 177-27-104 kilograms of NPK per hectare.

"We're trying to find alternatives to improve potassium efficiency," Dr. Dobermann says. Recycling more K through crop residues and breeding rice varieties with increased internal K use efficiency are the major mitigation options for reducing the predicted high K fertilizer rates to levels that are affordable to rice farmers in Asia."

The scientist predicts that future yield increases in irrigated rice can be achieved without applying excessive amounts of nitrogen, provided the average nitrogen use efficiency can be increased to levels currently achieved in well-managed field experiments. "And that means paying more attention to potassium to keep the balance," says Dr. Dobermann.

Communicating Pest Management to Millions

Many of the insecticide sprays farmers apply are either unnecessary or ineffective—and usually don't produce economic returns. So why do they use them?

In the early days of modern rice farming, insecticides were used to protect the plants from pests, with farmers encouraged to minimize their risks through insecticides. But then scientists began to develop varieties with resistance to pests that do not need chemical insecticides. Ecological studies now show that

applying insecticide early in the rice crop does more damage by killing the helpful predators than good for protection.

Communicating information to farmers about this change in concepts is challenging. Convincing even one farmer to spray less is difficult—so how do researchers go about changing the behavior of the world's 300 million rice farmers?

“Sociology and entomology must be integrated to change farmer perceptions and implement innovative IPM research,” says K.L. Heong, IRRI entomologist. “We need to distill science and make it understandable at the farmer level, or information will never reach the large potential audiences.”

So researchers used printed materials and a radio drama to motivate farmers in Vietnam to test the heuristic, or simple rule, “insecticides are not need-

ed in the first 40 days after sowing.” The information reached 97 percent of the 20,000 targeted farm households in Long An Province.

Eighteen months after the media campaign started, farmers' insecticide use was reduced by more than 50 percent, from 3.4 to 1.5 sprays per season with no yield loss; at 31 months, the mean was 1.8 sprays. The farmers believing that early season sprays were needed dropped from 77 to 23 percent.

The media campaign also went into neighboring districts with 210,000 farm households, where similar changes in spraying behavior were recorded.

Because the media approach is easy and inexpensive to adopt, 15 provincial governments decided to launch their own programs—at their own expense. These programs further communicated the heuristic to about

2 million farmer households in the Mekong Delta.

“This sends a strong message that to accelerate adoption, the innovation must be attractive to both the farmers adopting the practices and the implementers,” says Dr. Heong.

New Irrigated Rice Consortium

A great deal of time, effort and resources—both human and financial—go into irrigated rice research every year. But until early 1997, no single entity was providing direction for an international research agenda.

The Irrigated Rice Research Consortium was established to build a framework for the many collaborative efforts under way around Asia and to formally link the scientists who do the work.

“We envision the new Consortium to unite and focus the diverse research being done for irrigated rice so we can generate new technologies and recommendations and get them out to farmers faster,” says Robert Zeigler, IRRI irrigated rice program leader.

A steering committee, composed of senior members of national institutions and the IRRI program leader, guides operations.

The Consortium has already held two workshops and is focusing its initiatives on quantifying crop losses to pests under different soil fertility scenarios and determining how crop residue management influences soil health and pest populations. ■

The new plant type looking robust in the field

Rainfed Lowland Rice

Rainfed lowland rice grows in banded fields that are flooded for at least part of the cropping season. Grown on 36 million hectares—mostly in South and Southeast Asia—rainfed lowland rice makes up about one fourth of the world's total rice area. Because of the variable and heterogeneous environment, where flooding, drought, and problem soils prevail, rice yields average only 2.3 tons per hectare.

Depending on rainfall to grow rice involves risk: there may be too much water part of the year, and a water deficit at other times. Soil fertility is commonly low, and diseases—such as blast—may also reduce yields. An enormous challenge exists to increase productivity while sustaining the resource base in the diverse target areas.

Matching Plants with Unique Environments

In the heterogeneous rainfed environment, the best variety at one site is not necessarily the best at the next. Matching traits of a specific variety with dominant characteristics of a targeted rainfed lowland environment is one of the most promising approaches for increasing yields.

"The principal challenge plant breeders must address is the inconsistency of how varieties perform across rainfed lowland locations," says Len Wade, crop physiologist/agronomist and deputy leader for rainfed lowland rice.

Consequently, breeders need to identify those traits that make varieties more robust over a range of sites and seasons and then add specific traits for specific environments to capture the favorable genotype by environment interac-

tions. "Better understanding of these interactions will assist in developing varieties able to perform well in rainfed situations," explains Dr. Wade.

Scientists from IRRI and national agricultural research systems in Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand, through the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium, formed teams to identify the patterns of how varieties respond over locations and seasons, and the factors responsible for the patterns identified. From 1995 to 1997, a set of materials composed of popular varieties, advanced breeding lines, and some hybrids was compared at 10-12 sites each year.

"This work will identify key sites that are most effective for selecting for individual traits, such as tolerance for particular types of drought or submergence, or tolerance for soils of low pH or low nutrient levels," says Dr. Wade.

By identifying varieties that are especially sensitive or resistant to a particular problem and using them for checks—and by making selections at locations where particular problems are well expressed—better varieties should be identified more quickly.

New Varieties for Drought-Prone Rice Lands

Three hardy rice varieties for drought-prone rainfed lowlands are giving farmers more choices.

The Philippine Rice Research Institute has recommended the release of lines IR57515-PMI-8-1-1-SRN-1-1 as Sacobia, IR60267-11-2-2-1 as Bamban, and IR41431-68-1-2-3 as Tagatog for the drought-prone rainfed lowland areas in Central Luzon, Philippines.

The varieties, which were initially evaluated in Thailand

through efforts of the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium, yield 3-4 tons per hectare, have moderate resistance to major insect pests and diseases, and have good grain quality. The varieties are also adapted to grow well under direct-seeding conditions.

"These early maturing varieties make it easier for farmers to grow another crop after the rice is harvested," says Dr. Surapong Sarkarung, IRRI rainfed lowland rice breeder stationed in Thailand. "Our main goal is to breed varieties that will give farmers more options about what they plant."

Other promising breeding lines are being tested in drought-prone areas of Thailand and eastern India.

Improving Nutrient Use in Intensive Systems

Nitrogen fertilizer can dramatically boost crop yields, but when farmers apply too much the effects on the environment and human health can be extremely serious.

Scientists have been studying nitrogen use—and losses—at Batac, Ilocos Norte, Philippines, one of the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium sites, in a project coordinated by the Mariano Marcos State University and Philippine Rice Research Institute. The cropping systems in Ilocos Norte, which usually in-

volve rice and a dry-season vegetable (tomato, garlic, or sweet pepper), are highly profitable—and extremely input-intensive. Yet during the past few years, productivity has been declining, meaning that farmers must apply more and more inputs to get the same—or even smaller—yields.

“We’re finding that this intensive rainfed rice-based production system and others like it all around Asia may not be sustainable—economically or environmentally,” says J.K. Ladha, IRRI soil microbiologist.

When the soil is wet during the early rice crop, most of the nitrogen stays in the soil. But as the soil dries at the end of the rice crop, the trapped nitrogen changes into nitrate,

a form that is easily leached when the first rains come. Most of this nitrate goes straight into the groundwater.

At Batac, the average nitrogen lost per year is 270 kilograms per hectare, ranging from 240 kilograms when tobacco was grown after rice to 575 kilograms when sweet pepper was planted. More than half the wells sampled at the site had nitrate concentrations higher than the World Health Organization’s safe limits for drinking water.

The magnitude of N loss and its inefficient use in intensive rainfed lowland systems require changes in recommended fertilizer doses and application times, as well as the adoption of technologies to conserve and recycle nitrogen.

Better understanding of the basis of nutrient-water interactions will permit “smart”

L. WALSH/IRRI

fertilizers to be developed to better match soil nutrient supply and crop demand.

Some of the options being explored to improve the system’s sustainability are controlled-release fertilizers, improved timing of fertilizer doses, and integration of a catch crop between dry-season crops and rice.

“Smart” fertilizers—which supply nutrients to match crop demand—are being developed

“We are optimistic that the Batac site can serve as a model system for intensified and diversified cropping systems that can be applied to other rainfed lowland areas,” says Dr. Ladha. ■

Labor-saving direct seeding provides challenges for weed control and nutrient supply

Upland Rice

Nearly 100 million people depend on upland rice for their daily food. Many of the world's poorest farmers live in the uplands of Asia, Africa, and Latin America where farming systems are highly diverse.

Most upland farmers still grow traditional varieties without using fertilizers. More than 19 million hectares of upland rice are grown worldwide—around 63 percent of them in Asia. Upland rice areas vary in altitude from steeply sloping highlands of 2,500 meters to gently sloping areas only a few meters above sea level. The defining feature is not altitude but that upland rice grows on well-drained soils without standing water—just like any other crop.

Enhancing upland rice productivity provides an entry point to alleviating the interrelated problems of productivity, sustainability, and poverty.

Toward Perennial Upland Rice

Each year, more and more people try to eke out a living from Southeast Asia's uplands. But with arable land declining, there are no more of the long fallow periods needed to sustain the traditional slash-and-burn agricultural system. Increasing government concerns about sustainability, pollution, and food security are also adding pressure to move toward permanent cropping systems.

"Conserving the environment is rarely a priority for farmers when this activity conflicts with their need for food," explains Veronique Schmit, IRRI plant breeder.

A perennial upland rice could reconcile these interests by providing both food and erosion control. In a project

funded by the German Agency for Technical Cooperation, researchers have been working since 1995 to develop a perennial rice plant for the uplands. They started by evaluating wild rice species *Oryza rufipogon* (from Asia) and *O. longistaminata* (from Africa) for perennality and drought tolerance. *O. longistaminata* is extremely drought-hardy, thanks to its rhizomes.

After two years of screening, all the tested accessions of *O. longistaminata* survived, showing the ability of the species as a whole to survive drought.

But in *O. rufipogon*, strong differences in survival appeared, with the best individuals being from India and Myanmar. Fifteen individuals were selected based on their vigor and ability to regrow after cutting. These, and accessions of *O. longistaminata*, are

being used as donors of perennality in crosses with *O. sativa* upland cultivars.

Because a crossing barrier exists, the transfer of the rhizome trait from *O. longistaminata* to *O. sativa* is done through a complex scheme of crosses. Molecular markers linked with genes responsible for the presence of rhizomes and for their expression are being identified to help select for perennality.

As scientists identify resistance to the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola* in *O. longistaminata*, they are also testing hybrids for resistance. Molecular markers linked with the gene or genes of resistance to *M. graminicola* should be identified soon.

"Progress has been steady in this frontier project, and we are getting closer to a perennial rice plant for the uplands," says Dr. Schmit.

A. Rao, Lao PDR

Lowland Rice Critical for Preserving Uplands

Upland rice farmers in Cao Bang Province in northern Vietnam sometimes face serious food shortages. Despite living in the mountains, most of these farmers have small plots in the lowlands that provide more than half of their rice requirements.

"Increasing the productivity of lowland rice actually can directly improve food security of these farmers in upland areas," says Sushil Pandey, IRRI agricultural economist.

In a study to design technological, policy, and institutional interventions that will enhance food security of upland farmers and sustainability of upland systems, scientists have been working to first understand how Vietnamese farmers adapt their livelihood strategies to population pressure, market access, and government programs.

One of the most influential events occurred when collective rice farming was stopped in the late 1980s. Lowland rice productivity shot up with individual farmers caring for their own crops. Food security was improved in the upland areas and the environmentally unsustainable practice of producing rice using the slash-and-burn method was reduced.

Market access is critical in meeting the shortfall in food

production in bad years. In Vietnam, farmers in upland areas closer to markets can maintain basic food consumption by selling livestock. Their rice production may be lower than that of farmers in remote areas—but because those people are farther from markets, they do not have the same opportunities to bolster their incomes.

“The uplands and lowlands cannot be regarded as separate,” says Dr. Pandey. “To help upland farmers, we need to work in the lowlands, too.”

Farmers' Knowledge Priceless for Managing Diversity

In Lao PDR, the phrase for eating rice is synonymous with eating food—showing the importance of rice to the Lao people. Since 1995, researchers from the Lao De-

partment of Agriculture and Extension and IRRI have collected more than 10,000 samples of rice from around the country as a part of the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation project, “Safeguarding and Preservation of the Biodiversity of the Rice Gene Pool” (see story, p. 20).

“When collecting these seeds, we’ve been extremely conscious of also gathering information from the farmers about a variety’s vernacular name, origin, special traits, and significance,” explains Seepana Appa Rao, IRRI project scientist stationed in Lao PDR. “We realize that if we don’t, this priceless treasure of farmers’ knowledge will be lost.”

Lao farmers manage diversity on their farms very carefully—and sometimes even breed their own varieties.

The richness of rice diversity—and the information

about each variety—is fascinating. The variety *Khao Pong*, for example, was developed from plants that survived a prolonged flood; *Holo* was domesticated after it was found growing under a holo tree in a forest; *Poum pa* was developed using grains found in the intestines of a fish.

Farmers classify their varieties as upland and lowland, and by the number of days from sowing to harvest. They make the major distinction between sticky (*khao nieav*) and nonsticky (*khao chao*). “Sticky rice is preferred because it satisfies hunger longer, and it’s easier to carry to the workplace,” says Dr. Rao.

Some names explain domestic and cultural aspects of the rice. When the cooked rice of some varieties is somewhere between sticky and nonsticky, the quality is referred to as *khao manyeng*

(watching dog)—it is so inferior that even a dog prefers to look at it rather than eat it. *Mae may* (widow) produces some unfilled grains, while *Mehang* (divorced woman) produces a lot of grain, keeping the woman so busy harvesting the bountiful crop that her impatient husband left her.

“Indigenous knowledge enables scientists to select the most appropriate material to meet farmers’ future needs and for on-farm conservation,” explains Dr. Rao. “Quality is essential when developing improved materials for upland farmers—both for their own particular tastes and for selling value-added products in urban areas.” ■

Reaching new heights: Wild rice species *O. longistaminata* is helping make perennial upland rice a reality

Flood-Prone Rice

About 13 million hectares of rice land, mainly in South and Southeast Asia, experience uncontrolled flooding. Rice yields are low—often less than 1 ton per hectare—and extremely variable because of problem soils and unpredictable combinations of drought and flood.

Three major types of flood-prone rice exist: deepwater, which tolerates water depths of 50-100 centimeters; floating, which can be found in water ranging from 100 to 400 centimeters deep; and tidal wetland, which can survive short periods of submergence, sometimes in salty water.

Increasing the annual rice harvest in these areas is a critical social and economic challenge. Greater rice yields will improve the profitability of farming systems and the quality of life for millions of extremely poor people who must survive in these fragile flood-prone areas.

Making Rice More Nutritious

Anemia and very low immunity to diseases are chronic problems for poor women and children in Asia—mainly because of inadequate iron and zinc intake.

Rice, which is often their main food, already supplies nearly half their daily iron and zinc needs. But if these mineral contents could be increased, the health of these at-risk people could be improved without costly supplements.

Scientists have been examining the rice plant's reaction to low zinc availability and high iron content in the soil. This work was extended to find out if differences exist among varieties in transferring these elements to the grain. In collaborative research with IFPRI

and the University of Adelaide in Australia, scientists have found the grain of varieties to vary greatly in both iron and zinc. Of the 1,000 samples analyzed, iron in brown rice ranged from 7.5 to 24.4 parts per million (ppm), and zinc content from 15.9 to 58.4 ppm.

Traditional varieties adapted to harsh soils seem to have the edge over others—including modern varieties—for high iron and zinc. Floating rice Jalmagna, grown on alkaline soils in eastern India, for example, had almost twice as much iron as IR36 and nearly 40 percent more zinc than IR64.

"The soils of eastern India, which are iron and zinc deficient, definitely contribute to the origin of rice with high mineral content in the grain," explains Dharmawansa Senadhira, flood-prone rice program leader and plant breeder.

Some experiments conducted in collaboration with the Plant, Soil, and Nutrition Laboratory/United States Department of Agriculture in New York and the University of the Philippines Los Baños indicated that the extra iron in these varieties is available for human nutrition.

These iron- and zinc-rich traditional varieties are being crossed with modern rice varieties to increase yields and improve their resistance to insect pests and diseases.

"We think that the iron content of rice could be doubled, and zinc increased by about 60 percent," says Dr. Senadhira.

If breeders succeed in their efforts to increase the nutritional value of rice, it will indeed be good news for the women and children of the rice-eating world.

Outsmarting Acid Sulfate Soils in Vietnam

Acid sulfate soils are a perennial problem for rice farmers in Vietnam's Mekong Delta.

Acid sulfate soils are characterized by low pH and high concentrations of aluminum, sulfate, iron, and hydrogen sulfide. Over the years, farmers have developed a system in which they flush water over the soil to wash away some of the acidity. If they don't, rice cannot be grown. To prepare for the wet-season rice crop, this practice is usually carried out at the onset of the wet season when the acid buildup is greatest—and surface water is scarcest.

Scientists from Can Tho University, Wageningen Agricultural University, and IRRI observed some farmers who had devised a scheme to get around the water shortage problem—and boost their rice production in the process. Instead of flushing at the onset of the wet season, they do it at the end of the wet season as floodwaters are receding.

"There's less acidity to wash away because the soil hasn't been exposed to oxygen, and there's plenty of water to do the job—and to dilute the toxins," says To Phuc Tuong, IRRI water manage-

ment engineer. Farmers can then grow dry-season irrigated rice rather than deepwater rice, dramatically increasing their yields and lessening risks.

Scientists decided to put this intriguing technique to the test by using various combinations of flushing and harrowing, which breaks up the soil and exposes more aluminum to increase flushing efficiency. When three flushings and three harrowings were done in severely acidic soils, aluminum content was reduced and rice yields greatly increased.

“By leaching the soil when there’s less acidity and more water, and switching from deepwater to irrigated rice, farmers are helping the environment and improving their economic situation,” says Dr. Tuong. “Now we need to get the word out.”

Speeding up Breeding for Abiotic Stresses

Flood-prone rice plants are unique: they can survive flash floods, water as deep as 4 meters, and harsh soils. But they are also very low yielding because of the energy expended to cope with these stresses.

Creating improved flood-prone rice varieties requires breeders to retain these tolerances for abiotic stresses. Using conventional breeding techniques, however, has been time-consuming and costly. Efforts to breed salt-tolerant rice, for example, succeeded—but were slow. After 20 years’ work, only in 1995 were two improved salt-tolerant varieties (Bicol and Hagonoy) released in the Philippines. In

comparison, it took merely 4 years to produce IR8.

“Screening of new materials must be done in the field—and this takes time because salinity naturally varies across seasons and locations,” says Dr. Senadhira. The expense is also a burden: operational costs alone are US\$30 per plant.

Fortunately, biotechnology is providing an alternative. By applying molecular techniques, scientists are creating new opportunities for expediting breeding—especially through molecular marker-aided selection (MAS). The technique is highly reliable, economical (US\$2 per plant), fast (2-3 days compared with many seasons), and easy to use.

“The presence—or absence—of several genes of interest in one plant can also be

detected by analyzing a single DNA sample from a bit of leaf,” says Dr. Senadhira.

Progress has been considerable during the past few years. Major genes that govern tolerance for flash-flood submergence, salinity, phosphorus deficiency, and elongation in deep water have been mapped on chromosomes. Scientists have started to develop MAS techniques for these genes.

“With these techniques, we’ll be able to identify cultivars with tolerance for major abiotic stresses, which should allow us to cut costs and also expedite the development of improved flood-prone rice varieties,” says Dr. Senadhira. ■

Rice with high iron and zinc content may help improve the nutrition of women and children

Cross-Ecosystems Research

Prioritizing Rice Research

When it comes to allocating resources among research activities, policymakers, research administrators, and scientists often make decisions intuitively. To provide these decision makers with quantitative estimates on returns from research investment, scientists at IRRI worked with colleagues from national agricultural research systems (NARS) to undertake a study of farmers' perceptions of yield gaps and yield losses from biotic and abiotic constraints. The pro-

duction losses that could be eliminated by addressing these problems through research activities were then estimated.

Scientists and research managers met to review the findings of eight country/regional case studies and to examine the broader issues of research prioritization in view of recent developments in Asian rice economies.

"If the losses from specific constraints could be eliminated, yields could be increased by 40 percent with existing technologies and farmers' current management practices," says Mahabub Hossain, head of IRRI's Social Sciences Division.

According to the study results, nearly 8 percent of rice production is lost because of insect pests and rodents, 8 percent from diseases and weeds, and 20 percent from climate, water, and soil-related stresses. Stem borers, rice bugs, and brown planthoppers were identified as the major insect pests; bacterial blight, blast, tungro, and sheath blight as the major diseases; and zinc deficiency, unbalanced nutrition (potassium deficiency), and organic matter deficiency as the major soil-related stresses.

The importance of constraints varied enormously across regions and countries, although some problems are common: stem borers, brown planthoppers, leafhoppers, bacterial blight, blast, sheath blight, brown spot, weeds, rodents, and phosphorous, zinc, and potassium deficiencies.

"Some problems cause heavy losses at the regional and national levels though they're of less importance when losses are estimated at the international scale," cautions Dr. Hossain. Examples are ufra nematode in Vietnam, drought in eastern India, submergence in Bangladesh and eastern India, inadequate plant nutrition in Myanmar, thrips in Sri Lanka and eastern India, and iron toxicity in Sri Lanka.

"These findings suggest that NARS need to develop their own capacities for basic and strategic research for problems that are country-specific and depend on advanced research institutions and international centers to conduct basic and strategic research for problems of importance around the rice-growing world," explains Dr. Hossain.

A few problems—such as tungro, ufra nematode, and green leafhopper—were determined to be relatively rare but cause heavy damage when they do occur. "It would be more economical to address these problems through other policies—such as crop insurance—than through rice research," says Dr. Hossain.

The researchers also dealt with problems emerging because of the growing scarcity of labor and the changing preferences of rice consumers that are closely associated with economic prosperity. They recommended that higher priority be given to research for improving grain quality, increasing labor productivity, improving water use efficiency and weed management practices, and adding value to rice through postharvest operations.

"When formulating research strategies and priorities, decision makers must consider the stages of economic development in their own countries and regions," says Dr. Hossain.

Prioritizing rice research will help to alleviate poverty more quickly

E. Courtois, IRRI

Using Biotech to Target Bacterial Blight

Molecular approaches are being used with great success to combat bacterial blight (caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*), one of the most serious diseases in rice.

Scientists are using molecular markers to speed up breeding and to understand pathogen changes, and genetic transformation to produce transgenic rice (a normal rice plant with an alien gene or genes from another source, such as a wild relative of rice).

Since the early 1990s, IRRI scientists and their partners at Kansas State University have been developing a series of simple molecular markers to characterize the pathogen.

"Using these markers, we can now understand the pathogen's pattern of evolution over a broad geographic area," explains Hei Leung, IRRI plant pathologist.

This technology was transferred to the Asian Rice Biotechnology Network (ARBN), where scientists from several national agricultural research systems have determined the genetic composition of their local pathogen populations. They are using this knowledge to develop varieties with more durable resistance.

For host resistance, some of the most exciting work has centered on *Xa21*, a gene with broad resistance, which was first identified at IRRI in the wild relative of rice, *Oryza longistaminata*. Through conventional breeding and wide hybridization techniques, the gene was introduced into cultivated rice. A research group at Cornell University found molecular markers closely

linked to *Xa21*, which subsequently led to the isolation of the gene by researchers at the University of California at Davis. The cloned *Xa21* confers resistance just like that of the original gene from the wild species.

"While we recognize no single gene can offer a perfect solution to the disease problem, the cloning of *Xa21* has enabled researchers to move the gene rapidly into high-yielding rice varieties by transformation," Dr. Leung says. "The cloned gene also avoids the transfer of undesirable traits from wild rice—such as grain shattering."

Based on these efforts, IRRI scientists have produced a transgenic IR74 that carries *Xa21* and *Xa4*, another resistance gene; this prototype is now ready for field-testing.

In addition to the transgenic approach, ARBN and IRRI scientists have pyramided four bacterial blight resistance genes (*Xa4*, *xa5*, *xa13*, *Xa21*) into elite rice lines through marker-aided selection, and transferred resistance genes *xa5* and *xa13* to three new plant type lines.

Even greater opportunities are expected with the recent discovery that resistance genes from different plant species (tomato, tobacco, flax, and rice) have similar structures. "Plant species—much like animals—appear to adopt a common defense strategy to detect invaders," says Dr. Leung. "We can now use the common genetic information shared by diverse plant species to find resistance genes in species of our choice."

Within the next few years, this integration of biotechnology and breeding work will result in better bacterial blight-resistant varieties being released to farmers.

Ecoregional Initiative Breaking Barriers

Producing enough food to feed the world's ballooning population is a huge challenge. Creating sustainable systems in which to grow that food in harmony with the environment is even more challenging.

The "Ecoregional Initiative for the Humid and Subhumid Tropics and Subtropics of Asia" is working to develop models for conducting research to manage natural resources on a large scale.

"The opportunities for generalizing natural resources management research results from one site to wider domains are often limited," says Paul Teng, cross-ecosystems research program leader and initiative convenor. "Conceptualizing, conducting, and interpreting this research are best done by considering socioeconomic factors in regions that are defined by their biological and physical characteristics—not their political boundaries."

A diverse group of research partners is participating in the initiative: seven national agricultural research systems (NARS), eight international agricultural research centers, and three advanced research organizations. IRRI is the convening institution.

Developing knowledge bases and implementing case studies for soil erosion and diversification were singled out as priority research areas, and two pilot regions, the Red River Basin in Vietnam and the Chao Phraya Delta in Thailand, identified as research areas.

A regional working group was organized in each to define a scenario to improve natural resources management

and implement research and development activities.

Highlights from efforts in 1997 included conducting an ecoregional planning workshop for the Red River Basin and establishing the Systems Research Network (SYSNET) for developing methodologies to address natural resources management issues at the regional level. SYSNET is also working to train scientists in regional land-use systems analysis for identifying development potential and opportunities.

Through SYSNET, study sites were established in India, Malaysia, Philippines, and Vietnam to evaluate the models. An operational methodology was developed and applied, including holding consultative stakeholders' meetings. Training is a major emphasis: five workshops on crop modeling and linear programming were conducted, as were several sessions on geographic information systems.

Crop models and optimization software were also provided to NARS.

A decision support system was designed and general methodology agreed on, which was then applied in prototype models for the four study sites. Interactive workshops of stakeholders and scientists resulted in revised "optimum land-use allocation" models for three sites.

"There's a strong need for partners in an ecoregion to develop an organized framework for conducting this research and to share information before irreparable damage occurs to the environment and food production systems," concludes Dr. Teng. ■

Conserving and Promoting Genetic Diversity

Linking Farmers and Genebanks

Understanding how and why rice farmers select the varieties they grow is necessary for establishing dynamic on-farm conservation as a complement to preserving seeds in genebanks.

Scientists from IRRI and the Philippine Rice Research Institute interviewed farmers in 12 villages representative of the upland, rainfed lowland, and irrigated rice ecosystems in the Cagayan Valley, north-eastern Luzon, Philippines, and took samples of seeds from their fields.

The three ecosystems vary widely in genetic diversity, with the upland having the most and the irrigated the least. “This agrees with the hypothesis that agricultural intensification decreases genetic diversity,” says population geneticist Jean-Louis Pham, seconded from the Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération.

Very few of the samples collected in the farmers’ fields with the same name—including modern varieties—were actually the same genetically.

“Either a lot of outcrossing is occurring or some varieties have been misnamed,” explains Dr. Pham.

Farmers maintain traditional varieties because they have a distinct advantage over modern varieties under specific circumstances. In the upland ecosystem, grain quality was the main reason farmers continue to grow traditional varieties but, in the irrigated ecosystem, yield and short duration were key for growing modern varieties.

Short-duration varieties were also critical in the rainfed lowland ecosystem. Ironically, these modern varieties are attractive because they allow farmers to diversify their cropping system by growing cash crops, which increases their income and offsets pov-

erty. But these same modern varieties displace the longer duration traditional varieties, decreasing the diversity of the rice varieties grown by farmers.

Ultimately, however, it comes down to water. “While farmers may prize the taste or resilience of traditional varieties, it’s the presence or absence of water that determines whether a modern variety or a traditional variety is grown,” says Steve Morin, IRRI sociocultural anthropologist.

“Farmers’ knowledge is critical for determining which varieties do well under specific conditions and to understand their selection processes for establishing on-farm conservation,” says Dr. Pham.

Demystifying the Diversity of Wild Rice

Trying to figure out the genetic backgrounds of hundreds of samples of wild rice can be a painstaking task.

“Proper taxonomy of wild rice needs to be done,” says Bao-Rong Lu, IRRI germplasm specialist. “It’s like providing the basic alphabet to build meaningful sentences. Without it, we are not exactly sure

Understanding farmers’ knowledge is critical for on-farm conservation

about what we are conserving or using in breeding programs.”

Biosystematic research is improving that. By methodically studying the morphology, biochemistry, and genetic background of a particular wild rice sample, scientists can unlock its basic genetic information and determine its uniqueness—or similarity to other samples. Decisions can then be made with all the facts.

Scientists are first working to determine the biosystematic relationships and genetic diversity of the AA genome wild rice species. Once this is completed, they will plot the geographic distribution of each wild rice species and explain their evolutionary affinities.

“By obtaining detailed information, we improve our knowledge of the rice gene pool, which makes for more efficient use of diverse wild rice germplasm in breeding programs,” explains Dr. Lu.

New Information System for Biofertilizers

Biofertilizers, such as *Azolla* and blue-green algae, aquatic legumes and their symbiotic bacteria, and nitrogen-fixing bacteria, are small plants that manufacture their own nitrogen. When grown in a flooded rice field, they share some of this nitrogen with the crop.

IRRI has invested considerable effort in collecting, maintaining, and housing a large collection of these biofertilizers. “We have a responsibility to preserve these valuable materials and to share them with the world,” says J.K. Ladha, IRRI soil microbiologist.

The Biofertilizer Germplasm Information System (BIOFIS) aims to do exactly that. Expected to be online by 2000, the BIOFIS database will be a valuable resource for efficiently sharing information and processing germplasm requests.

“The huge task of organizing, compiling, and standardizing the information for each accession is currently under way,” says Teresita Ventura, senior research assistant.

This database is a component of the Global Microbial Database that IRRI and four other centers with biofertilizer collections are setting up as part of the CGIAR’s System-wide Genetic Resources Program. The International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas will house the central database. The target is to develop standards for these CGIAR microbial collections as well as a distribution policy in line with the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Sharing Rice Genetics with the World

To make rice genes work for people, diverse genetic resources need to be made available to researchers around the world.

Over the years, the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER) has played an important role in increasing rice diversity. Two hundred and twenty-two varieties released through INGER after 1976 can be traced to five or more ancestors, and 75 varieties have at least 15 parents.

In 1997, INGER continued its 23-year tradition of sharing by distributing 400 sets of the 1997 INGER nurseries for evaluation in 27 countries. Nearly 300 entries from the 1996 nurseries were used as parents in the breeding programs of 16 countries; 900 entries from 38 national agricultural research systems (NARS) and five international

agricultural research centers are being organized into 1998 nurseries.

To maintain viable and effective operations in a worldwide climate of financial cutbacks, INGER prioritized its test entries and nursery nominations and, in consultation with NARS coordinators, reduced test sites by more than half. Nevertheless, INGER remains an important germplasm exchange and evaluation network that IRRI is fully committed to support.

“With more focused testing of germplasm, and its targeted deployment in rice production environments, INGER will remain a highly dynamic network and continue to support the needs of rice breeders worldwide,” says Mike Jackson, head of IRRI’s Genetic Resources Center. ■

Young “helpers” collect wild rice in Cambodia

Information and Knowledge Exchange

IRRI Web Sites a Hit

Nearly 30,000 user sessions were registered in 1997 on the IRRI Web sites: Riceweb, the IRRI home page, and Rice-world.

"The users came from Georgetown, Guyana, to Beijing, China, and from all walks of life—scientists, journalists, teachers, students, farmers, and others who want-

ed to know more about rice," says Gene Hettel, head of IRRI's Communication and Publications Services.

Researchers are some of the top users of the sites. Annika Carlsson-Kanyama from Lund University in Sweden, for example, wanted to know the energy required to dry and mill rice, and Yuriko Yoshida from Japan asked about the role of African women in the Green Revolution.

Features about Vietnamese farmers on the IRRI home

page caught the eye of Emily Marlow, producer of the *TVE Earth Report* in the United Kingdom. She sent a film crew to southern Vietnam to record the experiences of these same farmers. The documentary will air later this year on BBC World Service Television, which has 50 million viewers.

The popularity of the IRRI sites is confirmed by the 1997 summary report of *Webtrends*, commissioned by the CGIAR. On the CGIAR web site <<http://www.cgiar.org>>, the

IRRI home page is the top entry and exit site of users looking for information about the 16 CGIAR centers.

IRRI Library Goes Global

These days, "global expansion" is the goal of more and more enterprises, and the IRRI Library Rice Bibliography is following the trend.

"Since its launch in the early 1960s, the Rice Bibliography has been the Library's flagship product," says Ian Wallace, IRRI librarian. "And now that it is available on the Internet, we can reach more scientists than ever before without increasing our costs."

The Rice Bibliography contains more than 170,000 references on rice, in at least 80 languages.

"English is the major language at 66 percent of the entries," says Editha Lantican, rice bibliographer. "Then Japanese at 19 percent, followed by Chinese at 7 percent."

Scientists around the world are searching the Rice Bibliography on the Internet. "They can 'save' references and send them to IRRI by e-mail,"

J. Veloso, Philippines

The IRRI Library provides local—and global—service

says Carmelita Austria, reference librarian. "Using specialized software, we can send the text of articles back to them, incredibly fast."

By taking advantage of modern technology, the IRRI Library is discovering that distance no longer hinders the flow of rice information to its clients. "Scientists in far-off countries are now almost as close to us as our colleagues in Los Baños," notes Mr. Wallace. "It's giving rice research a big boost."

Paper Publications Still Tops

Printed books, CD-ROMs, or the Web? Rice scientists and librarians from 60 countries were asked about their preferred format for receiving rice research information.

Three fourths of the 625 rice scientists said they still like paper publications the best, with 15 percent preferring information to be delivered through Web sites, and 11 percent, CD-ROMs. The preferences of the 165 librarians followed a similar pattern.

Forty percent of the scientists said their institutions have access to e-mail and 34 percent to the World WideWeb.

On the traditional publishing front, the Institute produced 11 books in 1997, either independently or in cooperation with major science publishing houses in Europe. Three issues of the *International Rice Research Notes* and five titles in the *IRRI Discussion Paper Series* were also produced and distributed.

"We also placed around 80 abstracts of scientific papers published in 1997-98 in the Science Online section of the

IRRI home page," adds Bill Hardy, science editor/publisher. <<http://www.cgiar.org/irri/Science.html>>

Visitors Keep Flocking to Riceworld

IRRI Riceworld, the world's only museum devoted to rice, attracts visitors from near and far—and lots of them.

More than 120,000 people visited the museum in 1997, up from 87,000 the year before.

"IRRI Riceworld has become a major tourist attraction in this part of the Philippines," says Mar Movillon, manager of IRRI's Visitors, Exhibition, and Conference Services.

After touring the museum, visitors know more about rice cultivation in general and also about what IRRI is doing to increase production worldwide.

"We see all sorts of visitors, from prime ministers to schoolchildren," Mr. Movillon says. "It is especially gratifying to see so many young people. After they leave Riceworld,

they have a new understanding of the important work IRRI is doing—now and in the future."

New exhibits will soon be offered to the public, including an expanded display on women in rice and a biotechnology exhibit.

Public Awareness Matches Audience Diversity

The "publics" who need to be regularly informed about IRRI, its research activities, and the impact of its scientific achievements are extremely diverse: national agricultural research systems, advanced research institutions, nongovernment organizations, farmers' organizations, donors, policymakers, media, academia, and other groups around the world.

To match this audience diversity in 1997, articles about IRRI and rice production-related activities were written and placed in prominent newspapers, magazines, newsletters, and Web sites, and broadcast on radio and television stations worldwide.

The Discovery Channel crew on location while filming a TV documentary on IRRI

Public awareness initiatives were to produce information materials targeted directly at the media of specific donors, and to share information with the public affairs units of donor organizations.

Highlights from the year included the following:

- "Rice to Feed the Hungry," a 16-page article on IRRI published in the *1998 Encyclopedia Britannica Year Book of Science and the Future*.
- A TV documentary on IRRI produced for airing in 1998 on The Discovery Channel (in English) and for dissemination in China (in Mandarin).
- Visiting international journalists and producers—16 print, 5 radio, and 4 television—featured IRRI.
- Thirteen international magazine articles on IRRI and its work, including two international in-flight magazines.
- Eighteen interviews with IRRI scientists taped for the BBC World Service's "The Farming World" radio program. ■

J. Viciano

Training

Exploring Internet-Based Education

For six years, a rice production research course has been taught at the Pathum Tahni Rice Research Center as a collaborative effort of Thailand's Rice Research Institute and IRRI. For the 1997 course, IRRI entomologist K.L. Heong served as one of the resource persons. But he was in the Philippines—and the participants were in Thailand. They were “net conferencing,” one of the newest ways to teach people across distances.

By harnessing the latest in information technology, the IRRI Training Center hopes to be able to reach more people than ever—and more cost effectively.

“Our aim is to provide another option for training rice scientists in support of IRRI's efforts to disseminate rice research information and technology,” says Robert Raab, acting head of the IRRI Training Center.

Distance education is a good way to help scientists from national agricultural research systems (NARS) keep up with advances in their fields. In traditional distance educa-

tion, delivery systems—such as mailed documents, radio, and television—are used to create a learning environment where trainees and instructors don't have to be together. And now, the World Wide Web has opened a new frontier of opportunities.

Although not all subjects can be taught across distance, many can be; and the potential benefits of Internet-based training are large:

- group interaction independent of time and space,
- quicker dissemination of information,
- improved availability of materials for training,

- reduced cost for producing materials,
- no travel and lodging expenses for trainees, and
- improved opportunities for collaboration between IRRI and NARS in implementing courses.

“We see participation in distance education as an excellent way to get NARS scientists up to speed on new ways to acquire information,” says Madz Quiamco, training specialist.

The Training Center is concentrating on three main distance education delivery systems: net conferencing, online Web courses, and Web-based publishing. “We think these can really improve IRRI's training capability without compromising learning outcomes,” says Dr. Raab.

Distance educators during the net conferencing session

Net Conferencing

Through net conferencing, scientists at IRRI will deliver lectures to participants of collaborative in-country training courses—just as Dr. Heong did in the trial run in 1997. In the one-way video and two-way audio lecture, Dr. Heong used slide-making graphics software to present his materials. A question-and-answer session followed, with course participants interacting freely with the lecturer.

“The trainees saw Dr. Heong and the lecture materials—but he didn’t see the trainees,” explains Pipot Abdon, training assistant. “They could, of course, all hear each other.” Aside from a few technical difficulties, the session went well—making IRRI trainers optimistic about using this method in the near future.

Online Web Courses

The Training Center and the Biometrics Unit jointly put together an online version of the Experimental Design and Data Analysis course. Once the course is up and running, instructors at IRRI will manage it and researchers from all over the world—even at remote sites—will enroll in it.

“The beauty is that participants can learn without taking time off from their work or leaving their families to come to IRRI,” Dr. Raab says.

E-mail and discussion groups will be used to provide opportunities for interaction between participants and the instructors and among the participants themselves. Trainees will also receive feedback from experts on exercises and actual problems.

The approach was tested in early 1998 with course participants at IRRI. The results, however, were less than opti-

mal, although the test may have been slightly unfair.

As Dr. Raab points out, “Learning over the Net was not the only option for these participants, so many chose to visit instructors in person rather than through their computers. But this wouldn’t be an option for participants far away.”

The materials will be retested under more realistic conditions to determine which types are effective using this communication medium.

Web-Based Publishing

The Training Center has redesigned and put online three training materials that support the IRRI Training-of-Trainers’ course. These are the performance objectives manual for the course and skills booklets.

“The results from initial activities have been promising, and solutions are in sight for the technical problems we encountered,” says Dr. Raab. IRRI and its collaborators will soon be sufficiently equipped to meet the challenge of using distance education technologies to provide NARS with access to training, materials, and expertise in rice science.

Training Achievements

- Provided degree and post-degree training for 148 scientists from 28 countries, mainly in Asia and the Pacific region.
- Eighty-six scholars, fellows, and on-the-job trainees completed their programs.
- Conducted 10 group courses at IRRI headquarters for 103 NARS scientists from 20 countries, bringing the to-

Learning to use new research tools is a feature of group training courses

tal number of scientists who have participated in group training courses at IRRI headquarters and in-country to about 9,160.

- Developed 13 instructional aids to document the technical content of five group training courses, and three Web versions of trainers’ manuals.
- Conducted eight national courses, providing 320 scientists from 13 countries with opportunities to update their skills.
- Produced three instructional videos for the Crop and Resource Management Network. ■

Strengthening International Partnerships

Cambodia Releases More “Lost” Rice Varieties

Three “new” traditional varieties are once again growing in Cambodian farmers’ fields.

The Varietal Recommendations Committee of Cambodia recently released three strongly photoperiod-sensitive varieties: CAR 11, a high-quality, medium-maturing variety with extra-long, slender grains; and two good-quality, late-maturing varieties—CAR 12 (with mild aroma) and CAR 13. The letters “CAR” signify Cambodian rice.

Cambodia’s rainfed lowland rice ecosystem is highly diverse, requiring varieties of different durations and photoperiod sensitivity: early (<120 days), medium (120-150 days), and late (>150 days).

“We’re trying to develop as many varieties as possible for each maturity group so that farmers have more choices,” explains Edwin Javier, Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP) plant breeder.

Because Cambodia had no cold storage facilities, its rice germplasm collection was sent to IRRI in the early 1970s for safekeeping. Many of these traditional varieties subse-

quently disappeared in Cambodia during the civil strife.

“When people were forced to relocate, they brought their own rice seeds, but often these varieties were not suited to the new area,” says Dr. Javier. In the 1980s, seed samples of the lost Cambodian rices were returned by IRRI at the government’s request.

“We can really attest to the value of conserving germplasm in the International Rice Genebank,” says the plant breeder. Eight of the 24 total varieties released since 1990 have been from these “lost” rice seeds—including CAR 11,

CAR 12, and CAR 13. The other varieties released have been from joint germplasm collection efforts of the Cambodian Department of Agronomy, provincial agriculture offices, NGOs, and CIAP.

Helping Farmers Stay Put in Lao PDR

In the northern part of Lao PDR, 300,000 farmers practice slash-and-burn agriculture, clearing an estimated 250,000-300,000 hectares of land every year.

To lessen this environmental onslaught, the government implemented a program to end shifting cultivation, decrease upland rice area, and improve the stability of upland systems. Land is being allocated to households based on family size, and crop diversification is being encouraged.

The Lao-IRRI Research and Training Project, supported by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation, is playing a major role in trying to develop techniques to help farmers cope with this drastic change in farming practices.

“Farmers are willing to shift to more stationary agricultural systems, but they just don’t know how,” explains Keith Fahrney, IRRI upland

Improved rice varieties are giving farmers more choices in Cambodia

agronomist. "Farmers and scientists working together is the best way to go about finding sustainable methods to produce food and improve the livelihoods for these people."

IRRI and Lao scientists are working to develop strategies to improve rice-based upland systems, including rotations of rice with cash crops and soil-improving crops, and soil conservation measures that encourage integrated landscape management—such as contour hedgerows to decrease soil loss.

They are also trying to find ways to make fallows more productive—and profitable. Raising livestock on legume fallow vegetation is one option; another is to plant small trees, such as paper mulberry, in fallow fields and sell the inner bark to make paper. This provides cash income for purchasing rice and extends the fallow duration, increasing efficiency of the restorative phase of the cropping system.

On-farm demonstrations are under way in four provinces in northern Lao PDR to determine which of the proposed innovations farmers find acceptable.

"These methods will ultimately help them in the transition from slash-and-burn to stable, integrated upland rice cropping systems as markets develop," says Dr. Fahrney.

Madagascar: Agriculture Key to Saving Environment

A rare combination of diversity and degree of threat has caused environmentalists to describe Madagascar as the world's highest priority for conservation efforts.

The island country is home to 25 percent of all African

plant species. About 80 percent of the country's plants are endemic—and the proportion is even higher for animals. Equally amazing, although negatively, is the high degree of environmental degradation: more than 80 percent of the country's original forest cover has already disappeared.

"Poverty and low agricultural productivity, compounded by rapid population growth, are now widely accepted as the main cause of natural resource degradation," says Martha Gaudreau, agronomist and team leader of the Madagascar-IRRI Rice Research Project. "Stabilizing rice production is the first step to preserving what remains of the forest."

There is a direct relationship between productivity of the lowlands and deforestation in regions where severe yield losses are caused by rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV). Farmers faced with such losses are forced to cut and burn forests and move into protected areas to cultivate upland rice, which is less susceptible to diseases but less productive than lowland rice. IRRI has been working in partnership with environmental organizations to spread the use of RYMV-resistant varieties in a concerted effort to protect the environment.

Rice farming is the single most important agricultural activity, and rice is the preferred staple food. The project, which began in 1984 and is supported by the United States Agency for International Development, strives to improve rice productivity in sustainable systems as a means to alleviate poverty and preserve the environment.

Highlights from 1997 activities included the following:

- Scientists have made good progress in breeding improved

varieties with resistance to RYMV—a serious disease in Madagascar and other parts of Africa—using sources of resistance from cultivated rice varieties and the wild rice *O. longistaminata*.

- The strategy linking the public sector, private sector, and NGOs in promoting agricultural mechanization started bearing fruit. A blacksmith association in the Northwest produced and sold 14 *tapak-tapak* water pumps, and a French NGO has sold five conopoddlers.

Identifying Cambodian Soils Made Easy

Agronomists and plant breeders in Cambodia are exploring interactions between soils and crop growth they never knew existed before—thanks to a new manual released by CIAP.

The Soils Used for Rice Production in Cambodia: A Manual for Their Recognition and Management takes a new approach to identifying soils so that even people without any formal training in soil science can easily identify them.

"The manual has been a revelation for Cambodian scientists who, until now, have had little soil information on which to base their work," explains Peter White, CIAP soil scientist and one of the manual's editors. Features that are easily detectable in the field, such as the landscape position and soil color, are used as criteria to distinguish soils.

"Now that we can easily identify the soils, we can use the manual to develop varieties better adapted to particular soils," says Men Sarom, senior plant breeder with the Cambodian Department of Agronomy.

CREMNET: Check the Color, Save Fertilizer

The leaf color chart—a handy plastic "ruler" with six shades of green on it to simulate the color of rice leaves—is catching on around Asia.

Simple and inexpensive, the chart is being advocated by CREMNET, the Crop and Resource Management Network, as a reliable tool for farmers to use to determine the timing of nitrogen top-dressing in rice.

"The leaf color chart is ideal for optimizing nitrogen regardless of the nutrient source, including biofertilizers," says Vethaiya Balasubramanian, CREMNET coordinator.

Five thousand charts have been produced and are being distributed to national collaborators and farmers' groups for evaluation around Asia. The Philippine Rice Research Institute and the Philippine Department of Agriculture have procured 15,000 charts to distribute nationwide.

By simply matching the color of a rice leaf to a shade of green on the chart, a farmer can determine the leaf color or intensity, which is directly related to leaf chlorophyll content—and nitrogen status. He or she can then decide the crop's need for nitrogen top-dressing.

The chart is based on a Japanese prototype.

CREMNET is a technology evaluation network that facilitates the free exchange, participatory evaluation, and adaptation of information-intensive crop and resource management technologies, methods, and tools for higher and sustainable productivity of rice-based cropping systems around Asia. ■

Finance and Administration

Changes in IRRILeadership

The IRRI senior management team underwent major changes during 1997 and early 1998. Dr. Robert Havener assumed the position of director general in an interim capacity in January 1998, replacing Dr. George Rothschild, who resigned in September 1997. Dr. Kenneth Fischer, deputy director general for research, served as

“If IRRI did not exist, it would have to be invented. As it does exist, it should be supported.”

5th External Program and Management Review Panel

acting director general during the transition period.

By the end of 1997, Mr. Michael Goon, deputy director general for finance and administration, and Mr. Edward Sayegh, director for finance, had both resigned to take positions at other CGIAR centers; in January 1998, Mr. James T. McMahon was appointed interim director for finance and administration.

Ms. Paulette Coburn has assumed the position of director for administration and human resources, and Mr. Gordon MacNeil will take over as director for finance.

IRRI Earns Good Marks in Review

The Institute underwent its fifth External Program and Management Review (EPMR) in 1997 and early 1998 and received good marks, despite challenging financial and staffing situations during the 5-year period.

The EPMR panel made several recommendations to improve the performance of the Institute, with IRRI management and the Board Executive Committee agreeing to most of them. The panel also made other observations and suggestions. These related primarily to program activities, such as further developing innovative biotechnology and bioinformatics approaches and the associated policy and operational guidelines related to intellectual property, and both public- and private-sector linkages in this rapidly evolving area.

One of the most important observations of the panel for the future of IRRI is the following: “Despite the recent difficulties, IRRI remains a strong flagship center in the CGIAR system whose scientific accomplishments during the review period are significant.... Similarly, IRRI’s relationships with its partner countries and their NARS, as well as with advanced laboratories worldwide, are impressive. The panel concluded that IRRI has a central role to play in future food security, and represents a high return to

investment that deserves the full support of the CGIAR.”

The review concluded that “if IRRI did not exist, it would have to be invented. As it does exist, it should be supported.”

“We fully expect the final outcome of the review to improve the performance of IRRI and enhance donor confidence in the important work and continued impact of the Institute,” says Dr. Havener.

National Staff Job Evaluation Under Way

A more integrated approach to human resources for IRRI’s nationally recruited staff members began in late 1997. The economic growth in the Philippines has dramatically changed demand for employees, resulting in IRRI facing increasing competition for staff members as industry moves closer to Los Baños.

Despite the 16-22 percent increase in salary given to staff members in 1997, several issues still require attention. One of the most urgent is the change in staff members’ job responsibilities as a result of the Staff Restructuring Program in early 1997. Another is for more opportunities for professional growth and performance-based rewards. A task force was created in December 1997 to study salaries, allowances, and other benefits.

Management strongly believes that these steps will again make IRRI a highly desirable employer.

Staying in Touch from the Field and Home

Providing state-of-the-art communication technology for IRRI staff members—in their offices and when they’re on the road—is the goal of the IRRI Computer Services Unit.

New “remote access service” has given researchers full computer network resources, such as e-mail and databases, when they travel in the Philippines as well as when they work at home.

A separate initiative has provided researchers with the ability to check their e-mail from almost any country in the world. By dialing a local telephone number to gain access to the Internet or the private SITA telephone network, staff members have read and sent e-mail from as far afield as China, India, and Mozambique.

“In the future, researchers will be able to access their e-mail using a Web browser on any computer that’s attached to the Internet and deal immediately with urgent requests from the office,” explains Ian Moore, head of IRRI Computer Services.

E-mail is not the only facility being used to improve communications.

“Collaborative applications will soon be available that will enable interactive communication using voice, video, chat, whiteboard, and sharing of applications among collaborators, partners, and farmers,” says Mr. Moore. ■

IRRI Financial Statements

IRRI's audited financial statements, which provide detailed information on the Institute's financial circumstances, are available from the office of the director for finance. The table below provides information on support from IRRI donors in 1997.

Financial support to IRRI agenda and nonagenda projects, 1997 (US\$)				
	Agenda		Nonagenda	Total
	Unrestricted	Restricted		
Japan	5,308,426	2,632,559		7,940,985
World Bank ^a	4,500,000			4,500,000
United States Agency for International Development	3,500,000		824,290	4,324,290
Switzerland		1,763,819	916,627	2,680,446
European Union		1,600,000		1,600,000
Denmark	1,139,049	242,126		1,381,175
Department for International Development, United Kingdom		1,098,126	162,967	1,261,093
Canadian International Development Agency	711,919			711,919
Australia	696,330	31,978	2,086,042	2,814,350
Swedish Agency for Research Cooperation	636,597			636,597
The Netherlands	256,032	532,318		788,350
The Rockefeller Foundation		717,536	392,094	1,109,630
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation, Germany	622,325			622,325
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation/German Agency for Technical Cooperation		622,331	273,433	895,764
Asian Development Bank		399,946	476,320	876,266
Republic of Korea	200,000	30,000	119,740	349,740
France ^b		215,306		215,306
Thailand	200,000			200,000
Philippines	189,069			189,069
India		150,000		150,000
Norway	145,964			145,964
People's Republic of China	90,000			90,000
Belgium	46,309		229,167	275,476
Spain	30,000			30,000
Indonesia	12,500			12,500
United Nations Development Programme			331,113	331,113
International Development Research Centre, Canada			102,232	102,232
Others			465,724	465,724
Total	18,284,520	10,036,045	6,379,749	34,700,314

^aIncludes a one-time payment of \$1 million toward 1997 funding shortfall.

^bThe Government of France, through the research organizations CIRAD-CA and ORSTOM, also provided IRRI the services of five resident scientists; the value of their contributions cannot be quantified.

How to Contact IRRI Offices

IRRI collaborates with scientists around the world. To support the Institute's global work, offices are maintained in 11 countries outside of the Philippines.

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¹Left during the year

²On study leave/training

³Joined and left during the year

⁴Joined during the year

⁵Cooperative research staff

⁶Joined in early 1998

IRS: internationally recruited staff

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Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR)
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Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO)
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Yanco Agricultural Research Institute

BANGLADESH

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Ministry of Agriculture

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Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF)
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Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS)
Chinese Academy of Science (CAS)
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Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences
Guangxi Academy of Agricultural Sciences
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(NARC)
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Kenya Agricultural Research Institute (KARI)

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KOREA, REPUBLIC OF

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LAO PDR

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NEPAL

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NETHERLANDS

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and Sustainable Agriculture (ILEIA)
Institute for Agrobiological and Soil Fertility
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Center for Agrobiological Research
and Theoretical Production Ecology

PAKISTAN

National Agricultural Research Center
(NARC)
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(PARC)

PAPUA NEW GUINEA

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PHILIPPINES

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Los Baños Science Community (LBSC)
Mariano Marcos State University (MMSU)
National Irrigation Authority (NIA)
National Postharvest Institute for Research and Extension (NAPHIRE)
Philippine Council for Agriculture and Resources Research and Development (PCARRD)
Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice)
University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB)
Visayas State College of Agriculture (ViSCA)
Western Mindanao State University (WeMSU)

SRI LANKA

Department of Agriculture of Sri Lanka

SWEDEN

Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA)

SWITZERLAND

Novartis Foundation for Sustainable Development
Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC)
The Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH)

TANZANIA

Ministry of Agriculture: Department of Research and Training

THAILAND

Asian Institute of Technology
Chiang Mai University
Department of Agriculture
Kasetsart University
Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives
Pathumthani Rice Research Center
Population and Community Development Association (PDA)
Prachinburi Rice Research Center
Rice Research Institute

UNITED KINGDOM

Department for International Development (DFID)
Imperial College, University of London
Institute of Arable Crops Research (IACR), Rothamsted Experimental Station
Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE)
Natural Environment Research Council
Natural Resources Institute (NRI)
Norman Borlaug Institute (NBI), De Monfort University
University of Birmingham
University of Nottingham

University of Oxford
University of Reading
University of Sheffield
University of Sussex

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
Ford Foundation
Michigan State University
National Seed Storage Laboratory, Fort Collins, Colorado
North Carolina State University
Ohio State University
Oregon State University
Rockefeller Foundation
Soil Management Collaborative Research Support Program
Texas A&M University
University of Arkansas
University of California, Davis
University of Florida
University of Georgia
University of Hawaii: IBSNAT Project, Nitrogen Fixation by Tropical Agricultural Legumes (NifTAL) Project, and the Research Corporation (RCUH)
University of Maryland, College Park
United States Agency for International Development (USAID)
United States Department of Agriculture (USDA): Agricultural Research Service
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Walt Disney World
Washington State University
Winrock International Institute for Agricultural Development

VIETNAM

Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI)
Institute of Food Crops Research
Institute of Plant Protection
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD)
Ministry of Education and Training (MET)
Department of Science, Technology, and Product Quality
University of Agriculture and Forestry (UAF), Ho Chi Minh City
University of Can Tho
Vietnam Agricultural Science Institute (VASI)

INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Asian Development Bank (ADB)
Asian Institute of Technology (AIT)
Asian Vegetable Research and Development Center (AVRDC)
Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI)
Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT)
Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo (CIMMYT)

Centro Internacional de la Papa (CIP)
Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)
International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD-World Bank)
International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA)
International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE)
International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management (ICLARM)
International Centre for Research in Agroforestry (ICRAF)
International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT)
International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC)
International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI)
International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD)
International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR)
International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)
International Irrigation Management Institute (IIMI)
International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI)
International Mycological Institute (IMI)
International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI)
International Service for National Agricultural Research (ISNAR)
Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA)
United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
UNDP: Global Resources Information Database Component (UNDP-GRID)
West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA)

Overview

Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR)

The CGIAR, an informal association of 57 public- and private-sector members from the South and North, provides the primary financial support for IRRI's work. It is co-sponsored by FAO, World Bank, UNDP, and UNEP.

The CGIAR envisions a world in which agricultural research has a positive impact on the lives of the poor. Through the work of IRRI and 15 other agricultural research centers, the CGIAR fulfills its mission to contribute, through its research, to promoting sustainable agriculture for food security in developing countries.

The CGIAR is committed to harnessing cutting-edge science to serve the needs of the poor and hungry. Through global partnership, the CGIAR is committed to alleviating poverty, increasing productivity and resource use efficiency to feed an expanding world population, conserving biodiversity, and protecting the environment.

One of the CGIAR's five major research thrusts over the next 20 years is to contribute to saving biodiversity. Under the auspices of FAO, the CGIAR holds in trust for the future one of the world's largest collections of genetic resources, containing more than 600,000 accessions of more than 3,000 crop, forage, and pasture species, both cultivated and wild. Duplicates of these materials are made available freely to researchers around the world. ■

“With all humility we can draw strength from the achievements of the CGIAR. They are real, have made a difference in the lives of countless people, and are so recognized.”

ISMAL SEREGELDIN, CGIAR Chairman

CGIAR Centers

CIAT	Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical Cali, Colombia
CIFOR	Center for International Forestry Research Jakarta, Indonesia
CIMMYT	Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo Mexico, Mexico
CIP	Centro Internacional de la Papa Lima, Peru
ICARDA	International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas Aleppo, Syrian Arab Republic
ICLARM	International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management Manila, Philippines
ICRAF	International Centre for Research in Agroforestry Nairobi, Kenya
ICRISAT	International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics Patancheru, India
IFPRI	International Food Policy Research Institute Washington, D.C., USA
IIMI	International Irrigation Management Institute Colombo, Sri Lanka
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Ibadan, Nigeria
ILRI	International Livestock Research Institute Nairobi, Kenya
IPGRI	International Plant Genetic Resources Institute Rome, Italy
IRRI	International Rice Research Institute Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines
ISNAR	International Service for National Agricultural Research The Hague, Netherlands
WARDA	West Africa Rice Development Association Bouake, Côte d'Ivoire

C. Hertel, Bhutan

C. Deodipri, Bangladesh

C. Deodipri, Madagascar

About the Cover

"As a conservationist and germplasm collector, I understand that rice genetic resources are humanity's hope and future, but I never realized that rice ecosystems could be so beautiful. When I go on wild rice collecting trips in Asia, I am often amazed by the gorgeous views of wild rice habitats, lowland and upland rice fields, and the other areas surrounding the fields. As an artist, I try to capture this beauty and charm, and express them on a piece of paper with watercolors."

B.R. Lu

The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) was established in 1960 by the Ford and Rockefeller Foundations with the help and approval of the Government of the Philippines.

Today IRRI is one of 16 nonprofit international research centers supported by the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The CGIAR is cosponsored by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Donor countries, international and regional organizations, and private foundations comprise its membership.

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